

HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS
IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

Deliverable D4.2

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

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HARMONISED PRACTICES, REGULATIONS AND STANDARDS IN WASTE MANAGEMENT AND DECOMMISSIONING

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- **pg:** 73

Executive Summary

The HARPERS Work Package 4 (WP4) has explored the integration of circular economy principles into the decommissioning of nuclear facilities and the management of radioactive waste across Europe. This approach can offer considerable benefits, including reduced waste generation, enhanced resource recovery, cost savings and improved sustainability. However, the implementation of circular economy in these areas may face significant challenges rooted mainly in regulatory constraints and public perception.

HARPERS WP4 identified key priority areas critical for circular economy and analysed existing regulatory discrepancies (Annex 6.1), case studies from various countries (Annex 6.2) and developed a decision support framework to compare linear and circular economy approaches in decommissioning and radioactive waste management (Annex 6.3).

This Position Paper outlines the integration of circular economy principles within the context of nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management, highlighting the potential benefits, challenges, and recommendations for implementation across Europe.

Section 1 discusses some nuclear industry challenges and how they can impact the implementation of circular economy principles in nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management.

Section 2 summarises practical experiences in implementing circular economy principles. They include implementation of the waste management hierarchy (reduce, reuse, recycle, recover, dispose). Examples include the recycling of slightly contaminated metals in Sweden and discussion on the reuse of contaminated concrete in Belgium. Such practices demonstrate the potential for reducing waste volumes and enhancing resource allocation efficiency.

Section 3 further discusses the challenges and opportunities associated with the integration of circular economy principles in nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management. It appears that regulatory constraints can complicate the establishment of a harmonised approach to radioactive waste and materials management across Europe. Clearance levels and conditions for recycling often vary, creating barriers to cooperation. The public remains sceptical about the recycling of radioactive materials, necessitating improved stakeholder engagement and dialog to build trust.

Section 4 summarises the main conclusions and HARPERS WP4 recommendations to facilitate the transition towards a (more) circular approach to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management:

- Harmonization of regulations: establish a European working group to develop unified guidelines for the release of materials from nuclear facilities.
- Development of best practices: develop a "code of practice" based on successful case studies to standardize procedures across member states.
- Centralized database: implement a shared database to document case studies of material release, enhancing transparency and facilitating regulatory interpretations.

- Public engagement initiatives: promote awareness campaigns and forums to address public concerns regarding radioactive material recycling.
- Collaborative research: encourage joint research projects focused on decontamination technologies and material characterization to improve processes for the conditional release of materials, making them safer and more efficient.

By addressing regulatory challenges and fostering collaboration among stakeholders, the nuclear industry can transition towards a more resource-efficient and sustainable future.

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CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY - 2 -

VERSION HISTORY - 7 -

1 INTRODUCTION..... - 8 -

1.1 NUCLEAR INDUSTRY AND CHALLENGES - 8 -

1.2 CIRCULAR ECONOMY AND BENEFITS - 9 -

1.3 HARPERS WP4 CONTEXT - 9 -

2 APPLICATIONS (CURRENT STATE) - 10 -

3 CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES..... - 11 -

3.1 POTENTIAL BENEFITS AND IMPACTS - 12 -

3.1.1 *Recycling and Reuse of Materials*..... - 12 -

3.1.2 *Reuse of Sites and Infrastructure*..... - 13 -

3.2 CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS - 14 -

3.3 POTENTIAL SOLUTIONS AND ONGOING R&D - 16 -

4 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS - 18 -

5 REFERENCES - 21 -

6 ANNEX - 23 -

6.1 T4.2A: NATIONAL REGULATIONS AND CRITERIA FOR CLEARANCE - SUMMARY RESULTS - 23 -

6.1.1 *Introduction*..... - 23 -

6.1.2 *Key Findings from the Questionnaire*..... - 23 -

6.1.3 *Insights from Workshops* - 24 -

6.1.4 *References* - 26 -

6.2 T4.2B: BENCHMARKING OF CIRCULAR ECONOMY APPROACHES AND TECHNOLOGIES – SUMMARY RESULTS..... - 28 -

6.2.1 *Introduction*..... - 28 -

6.2.2 *Overview of case studies*..... - 29 -

6.2.3 *Lessons Learnt*..... - 44 -

6.2.4 *References* - 45 -

6.3	T4.2C: SUSTAINABILITY ASSESSMENT – SUMMARY RESULTS	- 46 -
6.3.1	<i>Introduction</i>	- 46 -
6.3.2	<i>Methodology</i>	- 47 -
6.3.3	<i>Delphi study</i>	- 47 -
6.3.4	<i>Workshops</i>	- 48 -
6.3.5	<i>Results of the Delphi study</i>	- 52 -
6.3.6	<i>Case study: VLLW Management situation in France</i>	- 56 -
6.3.7	<i>Conclusions and recommendations</i>	- 70 -
6.3.8	<i>References</i>	- 71 -

FIGURE

Figure 4-1	- Suggestions for approaching harmonisation	- 21 -
Figure 6-1	- Waste Hierarchy	- 32 -
Figure 6-2	- Main drivers and opportunities for the recycling of CC concrete. Global overview based on the current situation in Belgium.	- 36 -
Figure 6-3	- Mobile sieving unit separating concrete rubble into multiple outputs with different granulometry.....	- 37 -
Figure 6-4	- CGR cyclotron on the former site of Best Medical Belgium, Fleurus, Belgium [6.2.7].	- 37 -
Figure 6-5	- First proposal of categories for the MCA (own work).....	- 47 -
Figure 6-6	- Selected categories and criteria for the first round Delphi study.....	- 47 -
Figure 6-7	- Poster presented at the HARPERS Subtask 4.2c workshop 1 in Brasov, for the identification of most relevant and redundant criteria.	- 50 -
Figure 6-8	- Aerial view of Cires.....	- 57 -
Figure 6-9	- Summary diagram of current management options for VLLW	- 59 -
Figure 6-10	- Acaci project to increase authorised disposal capacity at Cires.	- 63 -
Figure 6-11	- VLLW waste management options under consideration.	- 64 -
Figure 6-12	- Overall MS-MCA methodology developed in the PNGMDR 2022-2026 framework.....	- 65 -
Figure 6-13	- Main composition of the stakeholders group: ANCCLI - National Association of the Local Committee of Information; ASN - French Nuclear Safety Authority; CEA - The French Alternative Energies and Atomic Commission; CNE - National Evaluation Commission; DGPR - Risk Prevention Department (Ministry of the Environment); IRSN - Institute for Radiation Protection and Nuclear Safety.	- 66 -
Figure 6-14	- List of criteria selected for the analysis of the management options of VLLW-	67

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

TABLE

Table 6-1 - Differences in National Approaches - Summary Table - 24 -
Table 6-2 - Quantities of the materials/equipment of OPEC-2 considered for reuse, recycle or landfill. - 31 -
Table 6-3 - Radiological criteria considered for OPEC-2 refurbishment as a temporary storage facility. - 31 -
Table 6-4 - Summary of assessment of different disposal concepts with respect to a range of attributes..... - 33 -
Table 6-5 - Results of the Brasov workshop 1, representing the most critical and less critical criteria. The numbers indicate the sum of times a criterion was selected by different participants. - 51 -
Table 6-6 - Results of the Delphi study after two rounds of consultation with the stakeholders and final discussions during Workshop 2 - 53 -

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1 Introduction

It is recognized that the application of circular economy principles in nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management can lead to benefits such as minimizing waste, increasing resources efficiency or enhancing sustainability. Nevertheless, there are challenges ahead in implementing sustainability and circular economy approaches across Europe.

Based on the outcomes of a first identification of the main priority areas and a subsequent analysis of the existing challenges and well-established experiences, HARPERS WP4 addressed the conditions and opportunities for promoting circular economy approaches when managing materials and waste arising from nuclear decommissioning across Europe.

1.1 Nuclear Industry and challenges

Nuclear power plays an essential role in low-carbon electricity generation. As a sustainable energy source, a responsible waste management throughout the lifetime of nuclear power plants and other nuclear fuel cycle facilities, and, in particular, during the phase of decommissioning, is essential.

One of the most pressing issues is the growing volume of both non-radioactive and radioactive waste generated by decommissioning and requiring to be disposed of. Radioactive waste comprises a wide range of contaminated and activated waste streams from high-level to very low-level waste (HLW to VLLW). The latter category, by far the most predominant (over 90%), must be appropriately managed, ensuring nuclear safety and radiological protection standards are implemented while considering the potential for recovering valuable materials, the need to reduce the quantity of waste and to minimize environmental footprint.

However, due to the lack of technological development and existing regulatory frameworks, radioactive materials which could potentially be cleared or recycled are instead considered and managed as waste. The integration of circular economy principles into radioactive waste and material management offers a way to address these challenges.

By prioritising resource recovery, material reuse or the development of innovative decontamination techniques, the nuclear industry could reduce the volume of waste to be disposed of, while also conserving valuable resources. This approach also aligns with UN sustainability goals, specifically the UN's sustainability goals twelve (responsible consumption and production) and thirteen (climate action).

The nuclear sector is probably among the most tightly regulated industries. These regulations are of course essential, but they can sometimes limit the development of initiatives to promote better circular economy approaches. One example is the recycling of materials with very low levels of activity, which is still prohibited under some regulations. In this respect, it would be interesting to study the need for regulatory changes to encourage more recycling projects. When it comes to the development of circular economy initiatives, an important challenge to deal with is public perception. Indeed, the challenges of recycling very low-level waste faces

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

reluctance from the public notably because of the issues of traceability, health and environmental impacts, etc. That's why it's important to listen to these questions and consider how best to address them.

One of the objects of the work was to lay the foundations for a comparative framework that allows for the social demonstration of the benefits of the circular economy and an objective comparison with the linear economy. The current stage of methodology development has been realized through the involvement of expert groups and by summarizing the lessons from pilot projects (cf. Annex 6.3).

1.2 Circular economy and benefits

Definition of the circular economy in the context of nuclear decommissioning was obtained in HARPERS T4.2c based on experts' views and feedback during a Delphi study including two rounds of feedback and iteration through email and online workshop (see Annex 6.3).

The circular economy represents a model of production and consumption based on the efficient use of available resources in all phases; this is done by retaining assets and materials in circulation at their highest value for as long as possible, and minimizing waste, through processes like sharing, maintenance, repairing, reuse, refurbishment, remanufacturing, recovering, and recycling.

Therefore, application of circular economy principles in nuclear decommissioning is relevant both for new nuclear facilities (from the design and licensing stage) as well as for existing facilities, for instance through sharing facilities for waste processing, reuse of radioactive and non-radioactive materials and equipment, recycling of metal components, reuse of equipment parts and building materials in constructions projects, maintaining and repurposing buildings, e.g. for other industrial or medical uses.

A circular economy approach can result in decommissioning process innovation, reduced consumption of raw materials, decrease of radioactive and non-radioactive wastes generation, repurposing of facilities and/or sites, possibly lower cost and lower environmental pollution. More generally, as an economic model, Circular economy can contribute to sustainability, even if existing facilities were generally designed for a linear lifecycle, there is a great potential to align their approach to decommissioning with circularity principles.

1.3 HARPERS WP4 Context

The first phase of HARPERS WP4 was dedicated to the identification (through a deep stakeholder interaction) of priority areas for circular economy considerations [1]. The priority topics included: (i) National regulations and criteria for clearance, (ii) Benchmarking of circular economy approaches and technologies, (iii) Sustainability assessment.

Those topics were further analysed in the second phase of the project to:

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

- (i) identify the differences between national regulations, release criteria and methodological approaches, and their impact on the reuse and recycling of waste, to identify the advantages and weaknesses, as well as the points that could be balanced through greater cooperation and/or recommending good practice for wider use (summary results in Annex 6.1)
- (ii) collect and analyse actual examples and case studies highlighting implementation of circular economy approaches and technologies to the decommissioning of nuclear facilities and related radioactive waste and materials management (summary results in Annex 6.2)
- (iii) set up a robust decision support framework that enables comparison between linear and circular economy approaches in radioactive waste management and decommissioning (summary results in Annex 6.3)

All the collected data and outcomes have been summarised in this Position Paper on circular economy considerations.

2 Applications (current state)

In a circular economy, the value of products, materials and resources is maintained for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimized. Implementing the waste management hierarchy is one way to promote a circular economy. In practice, it can be achieved in several ways during decommissioning of nuclear facilities or in relation to radioactive waste and materials management. HARPERS WP4 analysed a number of examples to highlight good practices and draw lessons learned which could be of interest not only for decommissioning but also for operation and design of new nuclear facilities (see Annex 6.2). From the least to the most favourable option, the waste management hierarchy considers processes to reduce (minimize the amount of waste produced), reuse (use materials more than once), recycle (use materials to make new products), recover (recover energy and metals from waste) and dispose (safe disposal of waste).

Optimisation of waste management and following waste hierarchy principles is a regulatory requirement in the United Kingdom for licensees responsible for waste management and nuclear facility decommissioning. For example, in March 2019, the nuclear decommissioning authority (NDA) accepted a strategic change to the Trawsfynydd site end state. The new strategy allows the operator, Nuclear Restoration Services (NRS), to consider on-site disposal of radioactive materials and waste. The new strategy was supported by a multicriteria assessment based on the NDA value framework [2], which considered various human health and environmental protection-related indicators. Such an exercise proved to be a useful way to dialog with local stakeholders. Comparing different options highlighted that on-site disposal would lead to a reduction of radioactive waste volume to be disposed and associated minimisation of local disturbance and costs. It also reduced the amount of material needed to fill excavated areas.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Recycling of slightly contaminated metals is a well-established practice which has been performed in Sweden for almost four decades. The Czech operators of Temelin and Dukovany nuclear power plants relied on Cyclife facilities in Sweden for metal recycling. Such a practice has been recently considered in France (following a change in the regulatory framework) to reduce the amount of waste to be disposed in the Cires disposal facility.

Contaminated concrete can also be reused and even recycled, as outlined by Belgium R&D activities related to low carbon concrete and the recycling of contaminated concrete, or Andra R&D activities aiming at reusing slightly contaminated concrete as an infill material in radioactive waste disposal facilities.

Recovery of valuable materials such as copper from slightly contaminated electric cables also fits with circular economy approaches, as outlined by Czech nuclear licensees' practices. This approach was also investigated by Andra (Orcade R&D project). In the Czech Republic, slightly contaminated oil and plastic are recovered for heat production.

Refurbishing and repurposing of buildings (instead of new build) in the frame of a decommissioning project, as outlined in the Italian case study at the Casaccia site, is an effective approach to reducing material consumption. Considering repurposing a sustainable approach (energy efficiency, highly reliable equipment, etc.) also provides valuable benefits from a circular economy perspective.

Applying circular economy approaches and the waste management hierarchy is possible, while maintaining the highest nuclear safety and radiological protection standards. But it often requires regulatory flexibility, as outlined by case studies in the United Kingdom or France for instance. Decommissioning and radioactive waste and material management strategies are indeed strongly influenced by national contexts and regulations. Regulatory requirements should be commensurate to the level of risk.

Case studies show that innovative approaches can be considered with (sometimes) adequate evolution of the regulatory framework, and when supported by dialog with stakeholders. Multicriteria analysis allowing to score different options or strategies can be a useful tool to support such a dialog.

Apart from regulatory aspects, economic aspects remain a major aspect to consider when selecting the best strategy for radioactive waste and material management, site clean-up and decommissioning.

3 Challenges and opportunities

Decommissioning nuclear facilities consistently with circular economy principles presents both challenges and opportunities. This section explores the potential benefits and impacts of integrating circular economy principles into nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management, addressing both technical and regulatory aspects. It also considers the complexities associated with implementing circular economy principles in this context,

highlighting opportunities for innovation, requirements for regulatory evolution, and societal acceptance. By examining case studies and ongoing research, this work aims at providing a comprehensive overview of the pathways for a more sustainable and resource-efficient approach to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management.

3.1 Potential benefits and impacts

3.1.1 Recycling and Reuse of Materials

Recycling materials generated during decommissioning enables a more efficient use of available resources. Recycling of steel is a common practice within the nuclear industry. For materials where recycling is a less established practice, techniques and processes could be adapted from other industries. However, there may be some technical challenges associated with the application of these processes to radioactive materials and these processes are often more complex than direct disposal.

Recycling aligns with waste hierarchy principles, significantly reducing the demand for raw materials, energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. For instance, steel recycling mitigates the environmental impacts of ore mining and smelting, while recycling concrete avoids the need to quarry new aggregates. Recycling materials also reduces the need for disposal space. Construction and expansion of repositories use significant amounts of resources and materials.

Recycling materials has capital and operational costs, which must be balanced against the cost benefits seen. Depending on national context, material type and volume, there may be significant benefits, such as a reduction in disposal volumes and thus a reduction in repository capacity demand. This reduction may lower costs, as some types of repository disposal are costly (e.g. geological disposal), though others are relatively cost effective (e.g., VLLW disposal at CIREs in France). Furthermore, monetising recycled materials offers a secondary revenue stream.

Recycling materials may have an impact on operational safety when compared to disposal of the same material, due to the increased complexity. However, this is outweighed by the fact that recycling avoids the need for quarrying or mining to extract new materials, which are likely to have more significant impact on operational safety.

The circular economy approach promotes recycling, addressing societal expectations for sustainability and improving public perception of nuclear decommissioning practices. However, there can be stakeholder concerns around the traceability of recycled material. Experience in Sweden has shown that these concerns can be overcome with effective stakeholder dialog.

In order to realize the importance of releasing materials for the possibility of their recycling and reuse across Europe, starting from the IAEA open sources data available as well as illustrative information from some HARPERS partners, it has been estimated that within the EU (+ UK, Switzerland) up to 56 million tons of released materials (steel and concrete) from

decommissioning can be generated [3], opening up the possibility that these materials can be recirculated in the near future within the EU.

3.1.2 Reuse of Sites and Infrastructure

Refurbishment and life extension of existing plants and facilities, as well as reuse of components and repurposing of buildings for waste processing and storage, including the eventual post-decommissioning use of the site, are quite related to circularity principles. The use of material from demolished buildings as bulk to fill empty spaces is also consistent with circularity.

Important experience exists in this field, some of which has been collected in the case studies presented in Annex 6.2. They include examples of repurposing and refurbishing of existing buildings to allow their use as a temporary storage facility at the Casaccia site in Italy, and a strategic change in the UK Trawsfynydd site end state to include on-site disposal of some of the radioactive waste resulting from decommissioning as an option. These case studies highlight that comprehensive planning, including multicriteria assessment of the possible options, is important to allow the identification of issues and benefits of different options, and to ensure the optimal approach is adequately considered and selected. Evolution of regulation or development of standards have been identified as enablers for a more circular approach to reuse and refurbishing. Opportunities and challenges for reuse and repurposing of facilities and sites site have also been discussed during an IAEA Technical Meeting [3].

It was recognized that optimization in the use of available resources can contribute to sustainability. Implementing circular economy principles leads to a reduction in consumption of fresh resources (materials, energy) through reuse and repurposing.

A change of frame of reference should be promoted: from considering the nuclear facility as a liability that must be removed to the recognition of the value of the existing infrastructure and the possible beneficial uses for the community (sustaining jobs, developing opportunities for local enterprises/networks, attracting new investors).

Early stakeholder engagement and transparency in the decision-making processes is necessary to communicate and share visions and benefits of circular approaches and supports trust as well as awareness and understanding of potential value and options.

Cost aspects and timescale remain key considerations, in particular where there are substantial costs incurred in the short-term but that economic and environmental benefits may only be realized or visible in the longer term.

Some suggestions have been identified, by the experts participating in the IAEA Technical Meeting, to remove barriers to reuse and repurposing of nuclear facilities and sites including:

- Better alignment of key policies and drivers for implementing circular economy principles,

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

- Culture changes within the industry (from removing liability to shared value and beneficial uses) and the regulators (to enable and encourage more sustainable and circular decommissioning practices & facilitate repurposing/reuse options),
- Education/awareness of circular lifecycle perspectives for assets including sustainability, an integrated vision and a longer time frame perspective,
- Enhanced stakeholder engagement practices and decision making, grounded in community (shared) rather than corporate (owned) values,
- Economic considerations, including cost uncertainties and barriers,
- Sharing of experiences and lessons learned,
- Clear vision (and supporting tools), from the design stage, about design options and materials choices to facilitate reuse and repurposing.

3.2 Challenges and limitations

At the international level, the regulation of nuclear activities is overseen by agencies such as the IAEA and the European Commission, which provide comprehensive guidelines and legal frameworks to ensure safety, security, and sustainability of nuclear operations. These bodies emphasize the importance of safeguarding human health and the environment from the potentially harmful effects of ionizing radiation. As a result, regulatory frameworks are heavily focused on the safe disposal of radioactive waste, with stringent protocols for containment, long-term storage, and disposal.

One of the primary challenges in considering circular economy aspects related to the management of radioactive waste and materials at the international level is that these regulations are predominantly designed to prevent the spread of contamination, ensure the integrity of containment systems, and minimize exposure risks. This focus on radiological protection often undermines the principles of reuse and recycling, which involve extracting usable materials from waste and potentially reintroducing them into the production cycle. Moreover, international safety standards tend to be conservative by nature by mainly focusing on the radiation protection of the public, without paying enough attention that for very low levels of contamination the radiological risk is negligible. This is central to many radiation protection regulations, which can be a barrier to the promotion of new and potentially safer techniques for recycling or reusing radioactive materials. In particular, the issue of radioactive clearance - allowing materials to be deemed non-radioactive and returned to the economy - faces scrutiny. Achieving regulatory approval for clearance levels, where materials are deemed "safe" for reuse or recycling in non-nuclear industries, can be a protracted and contentious process, even when advancements suggest that certain materials could pose little or no risk.

At European level, different approaches exist to radioactive waste management. The regulatory frameworks for nuclear waste disposal, recycling, and reuse may differ significantly from one country to another, creating challenges for cross-border cooperation. Some countries

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

have made notable progress in recycling (see Annex 6.2), but challenges remain for countries who have a more conservative approach, placing greater emphasis on safe containment and long-term geological disposal.

While regulations are supposed to be based on the same EC radioactive waste directive, this heterogeneity in national regulations can impede the establishment of a unified, pan-European approach to radioactive waste management. In particular, the absence of harmonized standards for waste classification and disposal complicates efforts to implement circular economy practices across borders. To illustrate, some countries may allow the clearance of low-level radioactive materials, whereas others may limit such practices due to concerns about contamination risks or public perception. The result is an uneven playing field, where the potential benefits of recycling and reuse may be stifled by regulatory differences.

The essence of the circular economy for radioactive waste rests in the reuse and recycling of cleared materials. However, these practices face several key regulatory challenges:

1. **Clearance levels and material recycling:** one of the most challenging aspects is the establishment of clearance levels - the thresholds at which materials can be removed from the regulatory oversight of radioactive waste management. While materials such as metals or concrete can theoretically be cleaned and reused in non-nuclear industries, regulatory frameworks may impose tight limits on what can be considered "safe" for reuse. The process of determining clearance levels involves complex scientific assessments and extensive characterisation, which can delay or prevent the approval of recycling programs because of too long procedures.
2. **Long-term liability:** in some cases, countries can be reluctant to allow the reuse of radioactive materials without robust mechanism that may address future potential health or environmental issues. Regulatory frameworks must grapple with issues of long-term accountability, especially in the case of international transport and reuse of radioactive materials. Without clear mechanisms for tracking the lifecycle of recycled nuclear materials, operators may be unwilling to take on the risks associated with such practices because of the cost of traceability.

The reuse, recycling and clearance of decontaminated radioactive materials also faces various technical challenges:

1. The first challenge is to be able to have a sufficient amount of materials that can be potentially considered for reuse or recycling so that the implementation of a decontamination operation is profitable and that customers can be interested.
2. The second challenge is to be able to demonstrate that the materials concerned are well decontaminated and meet the radioactivity thresholds for declassifying these materials. This demonstration can involve measurements of very low radiological activities, which are not necessarily accessible with current measuring devices in an

industrial setting (i.e. not in the laboratory). It must also be demonstrated that the residual radiological level of these decontaminated materials is homogeneous in the matrix of these materials, some nuclear radiation may not be detected on the surface of these materials. The homogenous character then becomes a predominant characteristic that must be demonstrated.

The implementation of circular economy approaches in decommissioning and radioactive waste management faces also social challenges. Public perception towards the reuse and recycling of materials with traces of radioactivity is often affected by the stigma surrounding the nuclear industry. Environmental sustainability should be considered as a driving factor for public acceptance and a comparative framework that allows an analysis of solutions, based on technological opportunities and regulatory frameworks, should be developed for the social demonstration of the benefits of the circular economy in comparison with the linear economy.

As reported in Annex 6.3, a guidance framework based on a Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA) has been developed to integrate environmental, social, and economic factors in the comparison of different alternatives. This approach promotes flexibility and dialogue, facilitates traceable decision-making and foster collaboration among stakeholders. One of the most significant challenges in developing the framework for social evaluation is striking a balance between inclusiveness and practicality by limiting the number of criteria without compromising thoroughness. Additionally, the dynamic and context-specific nature of social factors further complicates the development of a universally applicable framework. Nevertheless, to ensure a holistic evaluation, it is common practice to begin with a broad set of criteria, which are then systematically refined to eliminate redundancies and exclude potentially irrelevant factors.

The HARPERS guidance for the sustainability assessment (see Annex 6.3) was developed through several months of preparation and multiple rounds of consultation. It was further refined through Delphi analysis and expert evaluations. The importance of clearly defined objectives, criteria and quantifiable indicators was highlighted as an essential part of the methodology for the comparison of linear and circular economy, providing a better understand of the issue and a clearer identification of benefits and challenges.

3.3 Potential solutions and ongoing R&D

The previous paragraph highlights some of the challenges in applying circular economy principles to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste and materials management. Legislative, technical, and social obstacles demand innovative solutions to overcome these barriers and, finally, ensuring more sustainable practices.

On the legislative front, the need for greater harmonization of national practices is evident, as varying legal frameworks often hinder the efficient implementation of circular economy strategies. A preliminary step involves exploring national regulatory boundaries and engaging

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

with authorities through existing case studies. These studies can create precedents and clarify interpretations for future applications of circular economy principles, while also helping to identify inconsistencies in current national regulations. Examples include the conditional release of contaminated concrete (Belgium – Tractebel [§ 6.2.2.3]) and metals (Belgium – SCK CEN [Ref. [5], [6]]; Sweden – Cyclife [§ 6.2.2.5]), as well as the release of small quantities of specific waste such as plastics, oil, and sludge (Czech Republic – Dukovany and Temelín NPPs [§ 6.2.2.6]). These studies offer insights into handling different materials and contamination levels under varied legal frameworks, providing valuable data for refining policies. Disseminating case study findings through European and international projects, such as HARPERS, can support national authorities in testing regulatory limits and provide international bodies like the IAEA with robust data to develop guidelines. Such harmonization efforts can lead to a more unified approach that benefits both regulators and industries.

Technically, optimizing treatment and separation methods is critical for recycling dismantled materials and minimizing radioactive waste fractions. Improved techniques can significantly enhance material recovery rates while ensuring that radioactive contaminants are safely managed. Advances in measurement and characterization techniques are equally vital, as precise analysis is essential for determining whether materials meet safety standards for reuse. A better and more fundamental understanding of the various separation techniques leads to a more accurate determination of the type and quantity of materials that can be recycled, thereby reducing the amount of radioactive waste. This necessitates a range of research initiatives, from applied to fundamental studies, which explore innovative technologies and methodologies. For instance, the SMELD project (Belgium – SCK CEN [Ref. [5], [6]]) explores metal melting processes to enhance radionuclide migration to slag, achieving higher decontamination factors. Similarly, ENEA (Italy) has investigated the impact of acid type and sample concentration on radiological characterisation measurements through Liquid Scintillation Counting for reaching the stringent clearance levels requested by Regulatory Authority for steel samples [7]. These efforts demonstrate how technical innovation can significantly improve recycling efficiency, reducing the environmental impact of nuclear decommissioning. Encouraging collaborations between research institutions and operators can accelerate the development of such technologies.

The societal impact of aligning nuclear decommissioning practices with circular economy principles is profound, as public perception plays a pivotal role in the acceptance of recycled materials. Transparent dialog with stakeholders, including governments, industries, and the public, can foster trust and acceptance of such practices. Initiating targeted projects to achieve

these objectives is strongly recommended, as these projects can serve as platforms for dialog and information-sharing. Additionally, educating stakeholders through new or adapted training programs focused on the unique challenges of circular economy applications in nuclear decommissioning is crucial. Such programs can help build technical expertise, increase awareness of the overall benefits of recycling, and address public concerns about radiological protection and environmental impact. Promoting these initiatives at both national and international levels can strengthen cooperation and lead to more consistent practices across countries.

4 Conclusion and Recommendations

As reported in the previous sections, integrating circular economy principles into nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste management can result in significant benefits:

- reducing consumption of raw materials,
- decrease of the amount of radioactive and non-radioactive wastes (by reusing and recycling as much as possible),
- optimising the use of available resources by repurposing of facilities and/or sites,
- lowering cost and environmental impacts,
- decommissioning process innovation.

Applying circular economy approaches can contribute to a more sustainable and resource-efficient approach to nuclear decommissioning and radioactive waste and materials management.

Some already well implemented practices exist (§ 2), but there are still several significant challenges to integrate circular economy principles in current and future decommissioning and waste management projects.

From a technical point of view, one of the main challenges is the limited capacity of existing technologies to decontaminate and detect slightly contaminated radioactive materials, which restricts their recyclability and reuse. Regarding the regulatory framework, differences in national regulations create ambiguity in the application of clearance levels, and treatment of the different material streams, leading to inconsistencies that may impact public acceptance and trust in radioactive materials management practices. In addition, public perception about recycling of radioactive materials remains a significant barrier. To address these challenges, it is essential to implement innovative solutions, to promote and support ongoing research and development, and to develop a robust evaluation framework that includes clearly defined and measurable criteria to assess the overall benefits of various strategies, as highlighted in case studies and Delphi evaluations described in the Annex 6.3.

From a **regulatory** perspective: a harmonization of radioactive materials clearance practices at the European level is needed, which could be achieved through the establishment of a

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

European working group to develop common guidelines. Recycling and reuse should be, in a way or another, considered in decommissioning plans, designs and permitting procedures, during both the preparatory and implementation phases.

From a **technical** point of view: the key point is to be able to meet the radiological thresholds that demonstrate that the materials are below the clearance levels. Research and development efforts should focus on improving decontamination technologies, optimizing separation processes to maximize the reuse of materials and improving techniques to enable easier and faster measurement of (volumetric) activity. Examples include the use of radionuclide analysis in SCK CEN's SMELD project to enhance the efficiency of metal melting processes [5], [6].

From a **social** perspective: promoting transparency and stakeholders' engagement practices is crucial for improving acceptance of radioactive material recycling. The creation of a shared database documenting case studies could strengthen trust among stakeholders.

Some Suggestions have been identified for approaching harmonization at European level:

1. **Establish a European Task Force or Working Group.** Create a dedicated task force under an existing European body such as the *European Atomic Energy Community (EURATOM)* or the *European Commission* to focus on harmonizing regulations for the conditional and unconditional release of materials (review radiation protection reports, e.g. RP89, 122, etc.). This task force could include representatives from regulatory bodies, the nuclear industry, and research institutions across member states to ensure broad input and expertise.
2. **Develop European technical guidelines based on best practices.** Introduce a set of European-wide guidelines or a "Code of Practice" that promotes waste hierarchy and outlines standardized procedures for the release, recycling and reuse of materials. These guidelines should be based on scientific research, practical case studies, and international standards (e.g., IAEA guidelines) to ensure consistency and transparency across countries.
3. **Implement a centralized database for Material Release, Recycling and Reuse Cases.** Create a shared European database documenting case studies of conditional and unconditional release, recycling and reuse. This database would provide transparency, allow stakeholders to learn from successful and unsuccessful cases, and serve as a reference for both authorities and industry to better interpret regulations in complex scenarios.
4. **Pilot Cross-Border Harmonization Projects.** Conduct pilot projects involving multiple European countries to test and refine harmonized release protocols. For example, joint initiatives could focus on specific material types, such as concrete or metal, allowing for a comparison of results and regulatory processes across borders.
5. **Foster Research Collaboration and Innovation.** Encourage collaborative research initiatives across European universities and research centres focusing on innovative decontamination and material characterization technologies. Funding programs such

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

as *Horizon Europe* could support projects aimed at improving processes for the conditional release of materials, making them safer and more efficient.

6. **Promote Public and Stakeholder Engagement.** Increase transparency and public understanding to build trust in the reuse of decommissioned materials. Organize workshops and public fora involving stakeholders such as environmental organizations, local communities, and industry representatives to ensure their concerns are addressed early in the process.
7. **Standardized Training and Certification Programs.** Develop standardized training programs for professionals involved in material handling, decontamination, and regulatory enforcement. A Europe-wide certification system would ensure consistency in the understanding and application of harmonized regulations and circular economy approaches.
8. **Legislative Roadmap with Phased Implementation.** Create a phased roadmap for regulatory harmonization, starting with simpler materials (e.g., metals, plastics) and progressing to more complex cases (e.g., mixed waste). This gradual approach would allow time for testing, refinement, and adjustment based on feedback and real-world application.

By adopting these recommendations and fostering a collaborative approach among stakeholders, the nuclear industry can effectively transition to a more sustainable and resource-efficient model, enhancing both operational practices and public acceptance of nuclear decommissioning processes.

Figure 4-1 - Suggestions for approaching harmonisation

5 References

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WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

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6.1 T4.2a: National Regulations and Criteria for Clearance - Summary Results

6.1.1 Introduction

6.1.1.1 Background and Objectives

The result of Phase 1 across technical work packages (WPs) 3-5 was the identification of key topics for further elaboration in Phase 2. One of these topics, under WP4, is **National Regulations and Criteria for Clearance**, designated as Task 4.2a. This task focuses on identifying differences in approaches and the main incentives and limiting factors in the application of national regulations on clearance, as well as their implications for promoting the **Circular economy** (particularly recycling and reuse).

The clearance of materials from nuclear installations is a key step in facilitating the reuse and recycling of these materials, in line with EU Directive 2013/59/Euratom. However, differences in the application of clearance criteria among Member States (MSs) pose challenges for harmonizing practices across the EU.

6.1.1.2 Methodology

To achieve the objectives of Task 4.2a, a structured **semi-quantitative questionnaire** was designed and distributed among participants in the HARPERS project, representing various MSs with nuclear programs (ongoing and terminated). The questionnaire focused on **five key aspects** based on the TECOP approach: technical, environmental, commercial (economic), organizational, and (socio-) political. Participants were asked about national regulations, the implementation of clearance thresholds, and the challenges they face in applying clearance regulations to promote recycling and reuse.

The results of the questionnaire were analysed qualitatively, allowing for a conceptual overview of the current state of clearance practices across the EU. The conclusions and recommendations from this process are based on **expert opinions** and aim to identify common understanding and majority agreement among stakeholders. Further insights were gathered during two workshops with stakeholders, held on **15 July 2024** and **17 October 2024**, which provided additional data and strategic recommendations.

6.1.2 Key Findings from the Questionnaire

The questionnaire was completed by 18 participants, representing 13 Member States. The participating countries included those with active nuclear energy programs¹, those that have previously generated electricity from nuclear power but have since decommissioned their facilities, and one country without a nuclear energy program (Norway). While the detailed

¹ For the purposes of the questionnaire, countries that use/used nuclear energy to generate electricity are distinguished. The assumption is that the challenges of large volumes of waste for disposal and recycling (concrete, metals) are/will be faced primarily by countries with nuclear power plants.

results of the questionnaire are available in the Inquiry report [1], the following is a summary of the key findings.

Main Differences in National Approaches

- **Clearance thresholds:** Most MSs have implemented the clearance thresholds defined in EU Directive 2013/59/Euratom, but several MSs have added national limitations or specific conditions that make the process more stringent. These additional requirements sometimes result in **inconsistencies in clearance practices** even among neighbouring countries, creating barriers to cross-border cooperation in recycling cleared materials.
- **Use of conditional clearance:** There is a wide variation in the application of conditional clearance. Some MSs have successfully integrated conditional clearance into their waste management frameworks, while others face significant regulatory or technical barriers, leading to **underutilization of this tool**.
- **Regulatory compliance:** national approaches for clearance are often time and cost demanding (technically and procedurally difficult to apply especially for MS with small amount of waste) and difficult to transfer between countries.
- **Public perception:** Attitudes toward the reuse of materials from nuclear installations remain a significant obstacle in several Member States, particularly in those where there is a lack of trust in the nuclear industry or concerns about the long-term safety of recycled materials. This situation reflects the discrepancy in the perception of nuclear-derived materials within conventional material or waste regulations.

Aspect	Implemented in Most MSs	Significant National Variations
Implementation of EU Directive	Yes	Some MSs apply additional national limits
Use of conditional clearance	Limited	Highly varied between MSs
Public perception of clearance	Mixed	Significant impact on policy decisions
Regulatory alignment	Partially	Discrepancy in the perception of nuclear-derived materials within conventional waste regulations

Table 6-1 - Differences in National Approaches - Summary Table

6.1.3 Insights from Workshops

6.1.3.1 Workshop 1 (15 July 2024) [2]

The workshop had the aim of presenting the preliminary results of the survey and gain feedback and advice from external stakeholders who were engaged through a series of questions/polls to gain stakeholder’s view and promote an open discussion.

During this workshop, participants identified additional challenges and opportunities:

- **Regulatory challenges:** Some MSs encounter difficulties when integrating cleared materials from nuclear installations into conventional material and waste management systems. These challenges are not solely due to regulatory inconsistencies but can also arise from factors such as varying levels of public acceptance or the absence of

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

adequate facilities and technologies for recycling. While different interpretations of EU Directive 2013/59/Euratom may contribute to these challenges, the issue is not uniformly present across all Member States, as demonstrated by successful examples in countries like Sweden. This highlights the need for clearer, more precise guidance at the EU level to address these obstacles.

- **Incentives:** Economic incentives for promoting the recycling and reuse of materials cleared from nuclear installations are lacking. Some stakeholders suggested the development of **EU-level funding mechanisms** to support innovation in recycling technologies and to incentivize operators to pursue clearance procedures more actively.
- **Technology needs:** Standardized **software tools** for calculating and implementing clearance scenarios would greatly assist in reducing administrative burdens. Participants highlighted the **lack of harmonized technical tools**, which often leads to delays and inefficiencies in clearance applications.

6.1.3.2 Workshop 2 (17 October 2024) [3]

The second workshop had the aim of presenting the main findings of Task 4.2a, providing conclusions and strategic recommendations.

- **Clearance process efficiency:** The need for a **faster, more transparent clearance process** was emphasized, with simpler and more user-friendly procedures for operators. **Specific examples** of best practices from countries like Sweden, Belgium or UK were mentioned, where streamlined processes have helped reduce time delays while maintaining safety standards.

6.1.3.3 Main Conclusions

- Release of materials (especially conditional) is a key procedure subject to regulation and authorization. Although the basic criterion conditions and limits are uniform within the EU, the national application practice and additional conditions make the procedure technically and organizationally demanding and difficult to transfer between countries.
- Harmonisation of approaches (well established good practices / guidance) at EU level will facilitate the clearance process and the recycling and reuse
- There is agreement that the subject of circularity can be a non-negligible amount of material recycled and reused (undue burner to disposal) and can contribute to reducing the carbon footprint. However, the complexity of the process requires appropriate incentives and R&D to support its implementation.

6.1.3.4 Strategic Recommendations

1. **Harmonized framework:** The European Commission (EC) should prioritize developing a **harmonized clearance methodology** and related tools, such as standardized software for clearance calculations, to ensure consistent application across MSs.

2. **Public engagement:** A focused communication strategy should address public concerns regarding the safety and environmental impact of reusing cleared materials.
3. **Economic incentives:** Funding mechanisms should be introduced to support the development of recycling technologies and facilitate the reuse of cleared materials.
4. **Information exchange platform:** Establishing a platform at the EU level to facilitate the sharing of experiences, good practices, and information (in common knowledge) on national clearance practices would promote better coordination and understanding between Member States. This would help address variations in implementation and support the development of more harmonized approaches across the EU.
5. **Coordination with conventional material management systems:** To facilitate the integration of cleared materials into conventional waste streams, it is important to address any challenges that may arise after materials are cleared from nuclear regulation. Although these materials meet all necessary regulatory criteria, they may still face obstacles, such as hesitancy from conventional waste operators or concerns about the adequacy of recycling infrastructure. Improving coordination and aligning acceptance practices between nuclear and conventional waste systems can help ensure that cleared materials are more readily integrated and reused, supporting broader Circular economy goals.
6. **Procedural efficiency and clarity:** While the current clearance limits are already stringent approaching the limits of technical measurability; there is no need for further tightening. Instead, efforts should focus on **making the clearance procedures faster and the methodologies clearer** for operators. Those implementing the rules often express frustration over the slow and burdensome process, which lags behind the fast pace of the market. Ensuring more **streamlined and transparent procedures** would help operators adapt to market demands without compromising safety.
7. **Harmonisation** could be promoted with **guidance at EU level** based on a **risk-based harmonized clearance and recycling concept** and with the definition of **clear scenarios** for the given material and its potential use. Moreover, integrated approaches, based on sustainability and circularity principles, should be supported by economic and environmental assessment
8. **Cross-border cooperation:** Establishing mechanisms for mutual recognition of clearance decisions is essential for promoting best practices among MSs. By recognizing each other's clearance decisions, valuable materials can be reused across the EU without being hindered by differing national regulations.

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6.2 T4.2b: Benchmarking of Circular economy Approaches and Technologies – Summary Results

6.2.1 Introduction

The overall objective of the European Union's transition from a linear economy (*take-make-use-dispose*) to a Circular economy (*regenerative growth model*) is to contribute to reducing pressure on natural resources while creating sustainable growth and jobs. Such a transition is essential to reduce the impacts of human economic activities on the environment, including on biodiversity. In a Circular economy, the value of products, materials and resources is maintained for as long as possible, and the generation of waste is minimized. To accelerate the EU's transition to a Circular economy, the European Commission adopted the new Circular economy action in March 2020 [6.2.1].

The principles of the Circular economy approach are generally described as follow [6.2.2]:

- Recovery and reuse: products and materials are designed to be recovered and reused at the end of their initial lifecycle, rather than being discarded,
- Repair and reuse: encouraging the repair and reuse of products to extend their useful life. This includes initiatives such as take-back systems, collection of used products, and repair and refurbishment services,
- High-quality recycling: promoting high-quality recycling to reintegrate recycled materials into the economy as new raw materials. This reduces reliance on virgin resources and decreases environmental impacts,
- Innovation and ecological design: encouraging innovation in product design to facilitate their recyclability and reuse. Products should be designed to be more durable, repairable, and recyclable,
- Waste reduction: minimizing waste generation by encouraging better resource use throughout the product lifecycle, from design to disposal.

HARPERS project aims to establish and clarify the benefits and added value of more aligned and harmonized regulations and standards for prioritized topics related to decommissioning and initial phases of radioactive waste handling. Within the project, WP4 addresses the conditions and opportunities for promoting Circular economy approaches when managing materials and waste arising from nuclear decommissioning across Europe.

During the 1st phase of the project, stakeholders' engagement helped to identify priority topics to be further investigated within WP4 [6.2.3]. The list of identified topics include benchmarking of approaches implemented in nuclear fields for reuse of structure, systems and components & available technologies and Circular economy approaches already implemented in non-nuclear field.

WP4 Task 4.2b addresses this issue by collecting and analysing case studies outlining implementation of Circular economy approaches and technologies to the decommissioning of nuclear facilities and related radioactive waste and materials management. The expected

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

outcome of the task is to support decision makers to make decisions for minimising waste and recovering and reusing valuable materials.

Harpers partners involved in WP4 Task 4.2b agreed on the following work program:

- Identifying relevant documents describing practical experiences and lessons learnt in and outside the nuclear field. Most meaningful documents will be identified and summarized, focusing on the scope of task 4.2b. Documents to be summarized will be shared between partners.
- Developing a common structure for all case studies (national context, description, lessons learnt, etc.) based on the TECOP approach as far as feasible (one or two aspects may not be covered). Partners will provide case studies summary/analysis based on the proposed structure. Case studies can cover a broad range of examples: re-use of component/structure, re-use of site, recycling of radioactive materials (metals, graphite, concrete, etc.), approaches for minimizing waste, etc.
- Organizing a dedicated 2-hours meeting between partners during which each partner will provide its own views on good practices, issues, regulatory aspects, etc., to identify common approaches and the main criteria/drivers for approach and technology selection.
- Organizing an online workshop to present the collected case studies and the lessons learned. During the workshop the approaches and criteria will be discussed, and additional input will be collected.

The following case studies were identified and discussed between partners:

- Repurposing and refurbishing of existing buildings (Italy),
- On-site and in-situ disposal of radioactive waste at Trawsfynydd Magnox power plant (UK),
- Concrete recycling in the framework of conditional clearance (Belgium),
- Industrial plan for the management of very low-level waste (France),
- Treatment and recycling of contaminated steel (Sweden),
- Releasing of small amounts of waste in the Czech Republic (Czech Republic).

This document provides an overview of the case studies and associated lessons learnt.

6.2.2 Overview of case studies

6.2.2.1 Repurposing and refurbishing of existing buildings (Italy)

This section describes the reuse of an existing building to temporary store legacy and other radioactive waste arising from nuclear decommissioning activities at the Casaccia research centre. The decommissioning plan was developed by Sogin to maximize the use of on-site available low level waste treatment, conditioning, and storage facilities. Indeed, there is no radioactive waste disposal facility in operation in Italy, while the decommissioning of a number of nuclear facilities is progressing. Considering this context, the reuse of on-site existing storage facilities (after refurbishing to meet appropriate technical safety requirements) has

been identified as the preferable option in comparison with the construction of new storage buildings. According to Sogin, the main drivers considered to select the best option were public perception and environmental impact reduction and the most significant barrier for the project implementation was linked with the unavailability (at the time of the project design) of clear guidance and regulations on requirements for such a strategic type of buildings.

The Casaccia research centre, located 30 km north-west of Rome, is a R&D site. In 2003, two nuclear facilities of the research centre were transferred to Sogin for decommissioning purpose, the IPU plant and the OPEC plant. The IPU plant was a pilot-scale MOX fuel fabrication plant operating from 1968 to 1986. The OPEC plant was dedicated to irradiated fuel examination. It consists of 2 buildings, OPEC-1 and OPEC-2. OPEC-1 hot cells plant was built at the beginning of the 1960ies for post-irradiation examination of light water reactor fuel. OPEC-2 was built in the 1970ies but was never operated. In addition to these facilities, Nucleco operates facilities for low level waste treatment, conditioning, and temporary storage on the Casaccia research centre. Prior to decommissioning activities, a Ministerial Commissioner Decree required Sogin to implement actions to progressively reduce the level of risk associated with nuclear facilities and materials in the Casaccia research centre.

The Sogin dismantling plan for IPU and OPEC plants is based on an integrated waste management strategy aiming at maximizing the use of the available Nucleco treatment and storage facilities and considering on-site temporary storage for both LLW and ILW. The strategy involves:

- The treatment, conditioning, and temporary storage of LLW at the onsite Nucleco facilities,
- The treatment, conditioning, and temporary storage of ILW and special nuclear materials in the OPEC and IPU plants.

Sogin proposed the repurposing of Sogin OPEC-2 building into a storage facility for unconditioned waste and waste arising from decommissioning. Prior to the refurbishment of OPEC-2, an analysis of materials and equipment in the OPEC-2 plant has been conducted to assess potential for reuse or recycling to minimize the volume of waste (see Table 6-2. Three categories were considered:

- Materials and equipment that can be reused during the refurbishing phase and operational phase (filters, glove boxes, lifting hooks, overhead crane, pipe fittings, etc.),
- Materials and equipment that can be recycled (various furniture and small tools);
- Materials and equipment to be sent to a landfill (materials with poor state of conservation or non-compliant with current regulations).

Category	Volume (m3)	Weight (kg)
Reusable	185,39	26 362
Recyclable	208,77	37 340
Waste	106,28	9 514

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Table 6-2 - Quantities of the materials/equipment of OPEC-2 considered for reuse, recycle or landfill.

Objectives, criteria, and project requirements were defined in accordance with national legislation. The operational life of the storage facility was set up to a minimum of 25 years. Radiological safety objectives are provided in Table 6-3.

Situation	Criteria
Normal operation	10 $\mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{y}^{-1}$
Foreseeable accidental situation	1-100 $\mu\text{Sv event}^{-1}$
Accident	1 mSv event^{-1}

Table 6-3 - Radiological criteria considered for OPEC-2 refurbishment as a temporary storage facility.

Sustainability and Circular economy aspects were also considered during the design phase:

- Highly reliable components to minimize maintenance,
- Energy-efficient components to reduce energy consumption,
- Specific surface materials solutions to allow decontamination and possibility for future reuse,
- Storage spaces designed without constraints on the ground to facilitate future reuse,
- Materials supplier and landfill selected to minimize transport.

Actions were implemented during OPEC-2 building refurbishment to optimize the use of resources. For instance, materials such as iron, copper and concrete were systematically separated and recovered. Removed steel components and overhead cranes were all reused off-site.

As previously mentioned, special attention was paid on the optimisation of OPEC-2 storage capacity. After refurbishment, OPEC-2 storage capacity is 2 300 packages (285 L stainless steel drums and concrete shells for high Pu waste content). A dedicated loading plan was developed.

The preliminary dismantling activities (removal of the components from the OPEC-2 building) started in 2008. Plant works started in 2013 and ended in 2017 with final checks on the repository safety systems. In 2018, the Italian Safety Authority issued the license for operation for the storage facility.

Comprehensive planning, technical studies, and dedicated engagement with regulatory authorities were required to overcome the challenges associated with the lack of existing guidance and regulatory requirements at the time of the project design.

The experience conducted in Casaccia site was one of the bases of the development of specific guidance about refurbishing of existing storage facilities in other Sogin sites.

In 2020 the Italian Safety authority (ISIN) issued a specific Technical Guide (TG n. 30) that collects the objectives, criteria and general safety and radiation protection requirements for the

design, construction, operation and decommissioning of temporary storage facilities for radioactive waste and irradiated fuel.

6.2.2.2 On-site and in-situ disposal of radioactive waste at Trawsfynydd Magnox power plant (UK)

The UK’s Nuclear Decommissioning Authority (NDA) owns 11 first generation nuclear power plants with 26 Magnox-type reactors undergoing decommissioning, including 2 at Trawsfynydd. The Trawsfynydd reactors were in operation until 1991. The ponds complex was used for the temporary storage of spent nuclear fuel. Following a period of pond storage, the spent fuel was shipped to Sellafield for reprocessing. Since 1995, a program of site decommissioning has been under way. The final aim of which is to enable release of the site from nuclear regulatory control, including from Radioactive Substances Regulation (RSR).

Waste producers in the UK are expected to implement the NDA’s waste hierarchy (Figure 6-1) when planning activities which may result in waste being generated. Implementing the waste hierarchy ensures that the impacts of waste management on the environment are duly considered and are consistent with the principles of Circular economy.

Figure 6-1 - Waste Hierarchy

The site end state is defined by NDA as ‘the condition of an entire site (including the land, structures and infrastructure) once decommissioning, and clean-up activities have ceased’. In March 2019, the NDA accepted a strategic change to the Trawsfynydd site end state (proposed by its operator Nuclear Restoration Services, NRS) to include on-site disposal (OSD) of some of the resulting radioactive waste. This strategy change was originally supported by a 2016 semi-quantitative comparison of discrete site end state options (Table 6-4). The options assessed against each other across a range of attributes were:

- Option A: physical removal and off-site disposal (the baseline option),
- Option B: ‘physical removal and purely *ex-situ* OSD and
- Option C: pure’ *in-situ* disposal (ISD).

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Scoring was done on a simple better/worse basis, in which green means that the option performs better than the other one or two (but not necessarily very well), and orange means that it performs worse. Note that the two worse options may not necessarily be equivalent in terms of worse performance.

Attribute name	Physical removal and disposal (A)	Physical removal off-site and situ disposal (B)	Pure ex-disposal on-site (C)	in-situ disposal
Lifecycle worker dose (man-mSv)	Orange	Orange	Green	Green
Conventional safety risk (workers)	Orange	Orange	Green	Green
Deployment difficulty	Orange	Orange	Green	Green
Time to end of liability	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
Lifecycle costs	Orange	Orange	Green	Green
Precautionary approach (safety)	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
Precautionary approach (environment)	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
Burden on future generations	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
Proximity	Orange	Green	Green	Green
Disturbances	Orange	Green	Green	Green
Susceptibility to future degradation	Green	Green	Orange	Orange
Development Status	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange
Dependence on other site facilities	Orange	Orange	Green	Green
Impact of loss of corporate records / memory	Green	Orange	Orange	Orange

Table 6-4 - Summary of assessment of different disposal concepts with respect to a range of attributes

Subsequently, more detailed evaluation of on-site and off-site disposal options at Trawsfynydd was carried out in order to provide stronger underpinning and justification for the preferred strategy.

Based solely on the assessment of attributes, option C performed similarly to option A and option B ranked worse. This tends to support a conclusion that pure ISD performs better than off-site disposal. More detailed consideration of strategic decommissioning options demonstrated that a hybrid I/OSD approach would be the optimal approach to decommissioning at Trawsfynydd, and this strategy has been subsequently endorsed by NDA. Adoption of this hybrid I/OSD approach will result in significant circular economic benefits:

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

- It avoids the consignment of significant amounts of waste to disposal at the LLWR or licensed landfills. These have limited capacity and, in the case of the Low Level Waste Repository (LLWR), require significant resource use to develop,
- It allows for the reuse of radioactive material as bulk void infill, avoiding the use of non-radioactive filler which could be used elsewhere,
- It results in a large reduction in the number of HGV miles required for off-site disposal because material does not need to be removed from the site.

6.2.2.3 Concrete recycling in the framework of conditional clearance (Belgium)

Radioactive concrete, in a broad range of activity levels, arises in large quantities as a result of the decommissioning of end-of-life nuclear facilities. Radioactive concrete can be distinguished into two main types, depending on the way it contains radioactivity, either as neutron activated concrete or as contaminated concrete, while a combination of both is also possible. Besides contaminated concrete, resulting from being in contact with airborne or liquid contamination (e.g. spills), concrete structures can become activated, as further explained in the next section. Non-radioactive nuclides, present as compound elements (e.g. C, Ca, Si) or trace elements (e.g. Co, Eu) will be transformed (activated) into radionuclides as a result of neutron fluxes passing through the concrete structures. Such activated structures often contain a variety of activation products², while in the case of clearance, most often ⁶⁰Co, ¹⁵²Eu and ¹⁵⁴Eu will have the highest contribution in relation to the clearance levels. Neutron activated concrete will be present during the decommissioning of the following types of nuclear facilities:

- Nuclear Power Plants (NPPs): the reinforced concrete cylindrical shell surrounding the Reactor Pressure Vessel (RPV), also known as the Biological Shield, will become activated. The volume of radioactive concrete (exceeding the Unconditional Clearance levels) depends on several parameters (e.g. reactor power, operating lifetime, chemical composition of the concrete) but could result in volumes up to several thousands of tons per reactor,
- Research reactors: sections of the reactor block, close to the core, will become activated. Due to the size and power of research reactors, the quantities of radioactive concrete will be significantly lower compared to an NPP,
- Medical nuclear facilities housing accelerators (e.g. linear accelerators, cyclotrons, proton therapy centres) also generate neutrons that could interact with the surrounding concrete structures like a cyclotron bunker or irradiation vaults for the production of medical radionuclides. Due to the large number of medical nuclear facilities all over the world, the overall volumes of radioactive concrete should not be neglected.

² ⁶⁰Co is mainly produced by the reaction $^{59}\text{Co}(n,\gamma)^{60}\text{Co}$, while Eu^{152} by the reaction $\text{Eu}^{151}(n,\gamma)\text{Eu}^{152}$.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Reduction in the volumes of radioactive concrete to be managed as radioactive waste are driven by several main factors like cost optimisation (reduction of waste management costs), sustainability (as concrete is a very carbon taxing material) and since there is only a limited disposal volume available within the radioactive waste repositories.

The International Legal Framework on Clearance, also known as the IAEA and European Basic Safety Standards (IAEA GSR Part III and 2013/59/EURATOM), has been transposed into Belgian legislation by means of the Royal Decree of 20/7/2001 also referred to as the ARBIS (Dutch) or RGPRI (French) [6.2.4]. Annex IB provides the activity levels (Bq/g) for Unconditional Clearance (UC). A specific case of clearance know as specific Clearance or Conditional Clearance (CC) could also be applied, allowing the nuclear licensee to clear material with increased activity concentration levels (Bq/g) while adhering to the constraint of the maximum individual effective dose of 10 μ Sv/year by means of a dedicated dose impact assessment. In Belgium, the requirements to make use of Conditional Clearance are described in article 18 of the ARBIS/RGPRI. The radiological exposure scenarios to be taken into account in the dose impact assessment are defined by the Federal Agency for Nuclear Control (FANC) [6.2.5]:

- Impact on the workers: Inhalation (by resuspension of dust and in case relevant of released gasses) and direct radiation,
- Impact on the public: Inhalation (of released gasses and/or by resuspension of dust), ingestion by leaching and transport by ground- and/or surface water and direct radiation due to contamination with irrigation water.

Conventional concrete industry

Concrete ranks as the third most widely used substance in the world, trailing only behind air and water. Its crucial role in human civilization is emphasized by the fact that it accounts for approximately 6 to 10% of global CO₂-emissions attributed to human activity. Nevertheless, it remains the most widely utilized construction material worldwide due to its many advantages like for instance Durability and Longevity, Versatility and Strength. As such, Tractebel is striving to make low carbon projects a reality, at the scale of buildings and larger infrastructures. To achieve reduced CO₂-emissions throughout the full life cycle of a project, the use of materials like Low Carbon Concrete is imperative [6.2.6]. The use of life cycle analysis tools helps monitor the embodied carbon footprint at each stage of design and construction, including future demolition and reuse.

Nuclear concrete industry

In the early days, when dealing with radioactive concrete (in between UC and CC activity levels), it would be considered as radioactive waste. In Belgium, that would imply conditioning of the CC concrete in concrete disposal containers followed by disposal in the near surface repository, currently under construction in Dessel. Implementation of different evacuation pathways instead of radioactive waste disposal for CC concrete are preferred. Three evacuation pathways or scenarios are considered and each of them is evaluated based on 3

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

drivers: Cost Optimisation, Sustainability and the available space constraint imposed by the repository (see Figure 6-2):

- Scenario 1 should be avoided as much as possible as it will result in large radioactive waste management costs, a large carbon footprint since no CC concrete recycling takes place and additional concrete and steel will be required for the engineered barriers of the repository. To conclude, it will also consume valuable space within the surface repository,
- The improved scenario 2 evacuates the CC concrete to a conventional (non-nuclear) landfill. Hence, the waste management costs, and carbon footprint will be reduced, and it will free up space in the repository for waste with an increased radiological inventory. Unfortunately, the concrete is not recycled and falls outside the Circular economy,
- Scenario 3 will be further assessed in the future and could be considered as the fully optimised evacuation pathway as it enables the CC concrete to be recycled in the conventional industry.

Figure 6-2 - Main drivers and opportunities for the recycling of CC concrete. Global overview based on the current situation in Belgium.

Conventional concrete recycling process

Recycled concrete, both as aggregates or mixed (new) concrete, has several end-use possibilities like for instance road infrastructure (foundation, backfills, concrete road slabs), foundation for landing strip in airports, foundation for parking lots. Based on existing insights, recycled concrete is mainly used as aggregates for foundations since recycled new concrete has to comply with high standards. In general, several recycling process steps will be performed on the concrete: a large wheel loader will feed the concrete crusher installation (to downsize the concrete blocks into concrete rubble and allow the separation of steel reinforcement bars) followed by a sieving step to separate the concrete rubble into multiple

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

outputs with different granulometry (see Figure 6-3). Based on the end-use of the recycled concrete, further recycling steps will be implemented.

Figure 6-3 - Mobile sieving unit separating concrete rubble into multiple outputs with different granulometry.

Case studies Belgium - Dose Impact Assessment

ONDRAF/NIRAS, the Belgian Radioactive Waste Management Organisation in Belgium, is since 2012 responsible for the decommissioning of a former medical radionuclide production facility located in Fleurus, Belgium. The facility housed 2 cyclotrons for the production of medical radionuclides by means of high energy proton beams. The protons impacted on targets, producing neutrons via spallation reactions, which, in turn, caused the activation of the concrete walls of the irradiation chambers. An impression of the CGR cyclotron is provided by Figure 6-4.

Figure 6-4 - CGR cyclotron on the former site of Best Medical Belgium, Fleurus, Belgium [6.2.7].

As a result of an extensive radiological characterisation campaign, about 2300 tons of activated concrete exceeding the UC levels will be generated during the future decommissioning of the facility, including both activated concrete blocks containing steel reinforcement bars as well as a concrete shaving dust resulting from decontamination activities.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Since the concrete is only slightly activated, disposal as radioactive waste in a nuclear repository would not have been justified. Therefore, ONDRAF Site Fleurus (ONSF) opted for the CC route, according to Art.18 of the ARBIS/RGPRI. As no operational process for the recycling of CC concrete was available, it was opted to evacuate the CC concrete to a conventional Class I landfill. In order to demonstrate the adherence to the individual 10 $\mu\text{Sv}/\text{y}$ dose threshold, a dose impact assessment had been performed by Tractebel and SCK CEN to ensure the disposal of the activated concrete would result in a trivial radiological exposure for the non-occupationally exposed workers and the public. The exposure pathways and corresponding parameters were defined and agreed upon by the different stakeholders. The following section provides a brief overview of the calculated exposure values for the different groups of workers as for the public:

- The truck drivers, responsible for the transport of the activated concrete from Fleurus to the landfill site, including inspection of the load and opening of the container, are expected to incur an annual individual dose of about 8 μSv . This dose is solely due to external irradiation and could be explained by the presence of strong gamma emitting activation products, mainly ^{60}Co and ^{152}Eu , the large number of transports required as well as the exposure time and distance between the truck driver and the activated concrete,
- The landfill workers, responsible for adding soil covering layers on top of the activated concrete (by using a crane) as well as performing other daily activities on the landfill (1800 h/year basis), are expected to incur an annual individual dose of about 6 μSv . This dose is solely due to external irradiation and could be explained by the large exposure time on the landfill site within the proximity of the buried activated concrete,
- For the public: the residence near the border (external irradiation as well as inhalation) of the landfill had been considered as well as exposure resulting from the food chain (ingestion by leached radionuclides into the groundwater and ingestion by atmospheric dispersion). The most conservative member of the public would be exposed to a dose of about 6 μSv . The largest dose contribution would be caused by external irradiation from the garden (4380 h/year basis) at a distance of 50 m from the landfill.

Based on this case study, the truck driver will be the most exposed individual as a non-occupationally exposed worker within the overall process. It should be noted that the radionuclide inventory of the concrete and corresponding exposure scenarios will define the exposure values throughout all process steps. For comparison, in case uranium contaminated concrete rubble (quite similar to uranium contaminated soil – see Annex III of [6.2.8]) would be considered, the most exposed worker would clearly be working on the landfill during the unloading of the truck and container, with a similar contribution from direct irradiation as well as radioactive dust inhalation. The truck driver would only incur a very limited level of exposure compared to the landfill worker. It can be noticed that the exposure breakdown for uranium contaminated concrete rubble is rather the opposite as for activated concrete as uranium is an alpha emitter, and consequently will contribute less to external irradiation but will have a large

impact by means of the inhalation pathway. Regarding public exposure, both case studies show similar results.

Conclusion and Outlook

As huge quantities of CC concrete are being produced in the ongoing and future nuclear decommissioning projects, recycling of those carbon-featuring material streams should be fostered. The conventional concrete industry is putting a lot of effort in the production of Low Carbon Concrete as well and the recycling of end-of-life concrete structures. In Belgium, CC concrete recycling is currently in the exploration phase by means of the execution of the following assessments to define the radiological impact and evaluate compliance with the 10 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ dose threshold:

- Identification of the end-use of the concrete, based on a diverse set of parameters, like for instance the quantities, physical-chemical properties and market demand regarding concrete recycling,
- Definition of the radiological exposure scenarios (external irradiation, dust inhalation, ingestion) for the non-occupationally exposed worker and public involved in the recycling process. A proper understanding of the different sub-processes will be mandatory as these contribute to the radiological impact. Parameters are for instance: distance between CC concrete (radiation source) and operator, exposure time, dust production during crushing activities (related to particle size, airborne contamination levels, ...),
- Derivation of the CC levels (Bq/g) by means of a Dose Impact Assessment, based on the concrete radiological inventory and corresponding radiological exposure scenarios. In order to be compliant with the 10 $\mu\text{Sv/y}$ dose threshold value, it could be required to perform certain concrete processing steps by occupationally exposed workers (e.g. concrete crushing in a nuclear licensed facility) or implementing mitigating actions, for instance driven by technological advancements, to further reduce exposure of non-occupationally exposed workers during the overall concrete recycling process.

6.2.2.4 Industrial plan for the management of very low-level waste (France)

The French regulation considers various categories of radioactive waste. Among them, very low-level wastes (VLLW) are mainly produced during operation, maintenance and, especially, decommissioning of nuclear facilities. Activity levels of VLLW is usually below 100 Bq.g^{-1} and may even not be detectable.

The French regulation related to the management of radioactive materials and wastes does not consider clearance for radioactive materials or waste as a management option. The French scheme for VLLW management has been thus almost purely linear and based on direct disposal in a dedicated facility managed by Andra, Cires. It is a one-of-a-kind disposal facility in France. Disposal cost at Cires is around 1 000 $\text{€}.\text{m}^{-3}$. Alternative routes to Cires can be considered, such as incineration of combustible VLLW at Cyclife France treatment plant, but for limited quantities only. Cyclife France cannot process more than 3 000 tons of solid waste and 3 000 tons of liquid waste per year.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Cires was licensed for the disposal of 650 000 m³ of VLLW and, as of 2023, 450 000 m³ of VLLW have been already disposed of. 80% of VLLW which are disposed of at Cires are metal waste, soil, and rubble. In 2023, VLLW production forecast estimate is close to 2 400 000 m³, which is roundly 4 times the initial disposal capacity of Cires. Alternative(s) to direct disposal of VLLW at Cires must be investigated, taking into account the following aspects:

- Knowledge of VLLW inventory to refine management options,
- Reduction of the volume of waste to be produced and disposed of,
- Promotion of Circular economy and sustainable development approaches,
- Anticipation the needs for disposal capacities.

The mid-term solution to cope with the limited Cires storage capacity is to increase the licensed disposal capacity of Cires from 650 00 up to 950 000 m³, while keeping the current footprint of the disposal area and maintaining the same standards of safety. The project ACACI aims at extending the operation for an additional 12 to 15 years. Andra formally submitted a regulatory request in April 2023, which is currently investigated by State services. Prior to this submission, a preliminary consultation was organized from May 5 to June 9, 2021. A public inquiry ended in 2024 with a positive opinion from the investigating commissioner. Works could start in 2024 or 2025. In addition to this project, considering that even a 950 000 m³ capacity will not be sufficient, Andra also began to work on a new disposal facility for VLLW to start operation around 2040, when Cires will reach saturation. To save disposal capacity of Cires and the future VLLW disposal facility, it could be envisaged to develop VLLW disposal facilities on or near sites generating large amount of VLLW. This would also limit transport of VLLW from producers to Cires. CEA, EDF, Framatome and Orano, with Andra, are carrying out a feasibility study for such facilities. This will include a comparative analysis of environmental impact of storages options. Consideration could also be given to dispose of VLLW waste in conventional hazardous waste disposal facilities. There are currently 4 conventional hazardous waste disposal facilities in France which are authorised to dispose of low-activity waste with natural occurring radionuclides (U and Th isotopes).

The French regulation enhances the importance of Circular economy and waste hierarchy approaches and methods, e.g. reduce, reuse, recycle, etc. Disposal should be the less preferable option for waste management. As far as VLLW are concerned, Article D.542-86 of Code de l'Environnement indicates that VLLW management scheme should '*preserves disposal capacity by taking into account the possibilities for increasing the density of the waste stored and for recycling certain types of VLL radioactive waste from the environment*'. Such a regulatory evolution facilitates moving from a linear to a more Circular economy model with regards to the management of VLLW in France.

Studies on alternatives to disposal of VLLW at Cires, such as recycling, began in 2016, in line with the national roadmap for radioactive waste and materials management. While alternative approaches are investigated, technical aspects, economic constraints, radiological protection requirements, waste characteristics and environmental impacts have to be considered.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

In February 2022, as a follow-up to a national debate on the national roadmap for radioactive waste and materials management, the regulatory framework for the management of VLLW did evolve, allowing for the recycling of metallic VLLW on a case-by-case basis. This evolution, allowing for recycling of metallic (only) VLLW, is a major shift in the French VLLW management framework.

EDF is currently planning to build an industrial facility (Technocentre) in order to recycle metallic VLLW produced by the dismantling of nuclear facilities (up to 500 000 tons). Technocentre could produce metal ingots which will be used in conventional industry. It is designed to process 25 000 tons of metal per year over 40 years of operation. Residues (10 to 15% of the flux) would be managed according to their characteristics and probably disposed of in Andra disposal facilities. A public debate on Technocentre was launched in 2024. The investment decision should be made within 5 years and commissioning of the plant is scheduled around 2030.

In addition to the Technocentre, other recycling projects are currently investigated in France. Electrical cables could account for 10% of the volume and 3% of the mass of VLLW which will be produced by nuclear facilities dismantling activities. The Andra Orcade R&D project aims at separating electrical cable components from VLLW fluxes for copper recycling. The industrial solution under consideration consists in developing a dedicated facility for separating the components of electrical cables (a radioactivity-free metal core and a peripheral polymer sheath with potentially surface contamination).

As part of on-going prospective studies, various concrete fragmentation and crushing processes are being studied by Andra to assess the feasibility of replacing the backfill materials currently used at Cires ($2\,500\text{ m}^3\cdot\text{y}^{-1}$) with crushed concrete rubble from the decommissioning of nuclear installations. A change in the regulations would be required before implementing such a process at an industrial scale.

6.2.2.5 Treatment and recycling of contaminated steel (Sweden)

Treatment of contaminated metals by melting in Sweden started in 1987 as a joint initiative by the licensees and the regulators. Steel is after concrete the most common material in a nuclear power plant and in other nuclear installations. Examples show that between 5-10% of the total mass in a nuclear power plant consists of ferrous materials. Most of this steel material can be subject to clearance and safe recycling into new products on the conventional market. One of the keys to have metals in a circular flow is to keep different materials and qualities apart, to the extent practically possible. Over the years, the Studsvik facility and its operations have grown, including advanced equipment for decontamination, segmentation, and treatment of large components. More than 50 000 tons of metals have been melted. In addition, several thousands of tons have been cleared and released without homogenization by melting.

The treatment methods have been extended and enhanced over the years, as well as the type of metals possible to treat aiming for clearance. On average, more than 95% of the metals melted have been subject to clearance and recycling into new products.

The metal treatment process employs a carefully structured multi-step approach to ensure that the material sent for treatment can be safely processed, that the final outcome is accurately predicted, and that the metals are safely cleared and recycled back into the conventional industry. To achieve these goals, the approach incorporates several lines of defence. The typical metal treatment process can be divided into the following steps:

1. Pre-shipment activities: The potential customer is asked to provide radiological and physical data for the objects and to confirm that the materials meet the Metal Acceptance Criteria (MAC) for treatment. This is the first layer of defence. Prior to shipment, a treatability review of the data provided by the customer is performed. This is the second layer of defence.
2. Shipment and arrival of material for treatment: The set-up of the pre-treatment operations varies, depending on the physical and radiological properties of the objects. It may contain disassembly and segmentation operations, segregation, and sorting activities, as well as different types of decontamination operations aiming to reduce the radioactivity concentration and to remove paint and other surface coatings from the material. For certain key nuclides which alloy with the metal, like Co-60, the residual activity in the material must be reduced below the clearance threshold values in the pre-treatment operations. The typical method is abrasive grit blasting, which effectively removes the surface of the materials and by then the surface contamination. The visual inspection and the verification measurements after the decontamination operations are essential and provide another layer of defence.
3. Pre-melting operations,
4. Melting: melting in the induction furnaces at the facility homogenizes the metal and ensures the transfer of certain key nuclides transfer from the metal to the slag or to the off-gas filters while it densifies the material. Sampling is performed after the slag removal, but prior to the casting of the molten metal. The samples taken are proven representative of the entire melting batch.
5. Post-treatment activities: The residual waste from treatment operations, approximately 5% of the initial weight, is collected and packed into drums or other suitable primary packages. The primary packages are assessed. The treatment campaign is recorded in both the waste management database and a comprehensive treatment report.
6. Reporting,
7. Return of residual waste.

Each melting batch receives a set of fully representative samples for the ingots produced. Those samples are analysed and used as input for the clearance and release process. The produced ingots are released either unrestricted (general clearance) or with conditions (specific clearance).

Melting of contaminated metals aiming for clearance in a nuclear licensed facility brings several advantages and is considered as a proven and robust method to convert a liability to an asset. A few examples of the benefits are:

- More metal can be subject to clearance and recycling instead of being isolated,
- Separation of critical nuclides from the metal (alphas, Cs, Sr),
- Representative sampling and high precision analysis,
- Homogenization of the residual radioactivity in the metal matrix,
- Minimization of radioactivity release during further handling and melting of the metal.

6.2.2.6 Releasing of small amounts of minor waste in the Czech Republic

Two nuclear power plants are in operation in the Czech Republic, Temelín and Dukovany nuclear power plants. Low and medium level waste from operation is continuously collected and sorted. About 70% of waste generated in the nuclear part is capable of being released in the long term. Most of it is released under a conditional release regime and unconditional release is only applied to a very limited extent. This section is focused on the management of different slightly contaminated materials: plastics, oils, sludge, metals and building debris.

The following approach is usually considered to define to best option for radioactive waste management. A preliminary sorting is based on the dose rate of the item or piece (below 1 $\mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$) and the type of material. It aims at maximizing the volume of waste released from the scope of nuclear regulation. Operational experience shows that 99% of that waste with a dose rate below 1 $\mu\text{Sv}\cdot\text{h}^{-1}$ can be released. The remaining 1% is sent to the radioactive waste stream. After preliminary sorting, waste is measured in the MERLIN volumetric measuring device. MDA (minimum detected activity) values are used for protocol reporting of measurement results and scenario calculations, unless a real activity value has been measured. Current cost of the MERLIN volumetric measuring device for release is 2.2 $\text{€}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$. The costs of radiochemical analysis (determination of the radionuclide vector and derivation of correlation factors), packaging and transportation are 3.5 $\text{€}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ at Dukovany NPP and 6.1 $\text{€}\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}$ at Temelín NPP. The difference is due to higher transport costs as Temelín is 150 km away from Dukovany where the MERLIN device is located.

Plastics sorted according to the procedure are crushed on equipment at the public municipal landfill in Petrůvky and subsequently burned in the cement plant at Práchev to produce heat. Plastic recycling currently seems unrealistic as it is not possible to ensure back tracking. The total volume of plastics sorted and released in this way since 2012 for both power plants is 12.4 m^3 . The cement plant in Práchev also takes oil free of charge as fuel. From both NPPs is released and burn a total of approx. 20 m^3 per year.

Sludge cannot be stored in a municipal waste dump (as depositing sludge in landfills is generally prohibited in the Czech Republic) and is taken to a composting plant. Sludge is treated in the composting plant by biological, chemical, or thermal treatment. After treatment, ordinary sludge is mostly used in agriculture. But it is not possible to determine exactly where specific sludge ended up, i.e. to meet the conditional release requirement for back tracking.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Although it is declared that Cs-137 is <3 Bq/kg, i.e. thirty times below the release level (100 Bq/kg), yet the composting plant operator is afraid of the declaration of activity. There is a conflict between two different legislative regulations: the Atomic Act versus the Waste Act.

The Cyclife facility in Sweden is used for metal recycling. The Co-60 content is usually the limiting factor for conversion by melting, but the metallic material can be left in the decay warehouse after conversion before released into circulation. Approximately 1 000 tons of metals were released at the Dukovany NPP between 2011 and 2023, of which 88% was structural steel, 6% special stainless steel, 3.5% aluminium and 2.5% copper from cables. About 180 tons of metals were released at the Temelín NPP during the same period, of which about 70% was structural steel, 15% special stainless steel, 3% aluminium and 12% copper from cables.

Building debris and rubble are transported in 200 l drums for measurement in the MERLIN facility and then to the Petrůvky landfill, where it is used as backfill material. Large volume may raise some issues related to the number of drums needed for transportation and also the increasing price for transportation, especially for debris from the Temelín NPP when it is transported over 150 km.

Between 2011 and 2023, approx. 275 m³ of debris was released from the Dukovany NPP, and 36 m³ from the Temelín NPP.

Overall, about 130 tons of below-limit waste is released annually from Temelin and Dukovany NPPs of which 75% consists of metals (recycled in metallurgy), construction debris (used as backfill at the inert waste dump) and oil (used as energy raw material for the cement plant). Sludge from the sewage treatment plant is released (after clearance measurements) to the compost plant. Attention is paid to plastics that are used for energy purposes (burned together with oil). The NPP staff has procedures that, based on simple measurements and operational experience, enable to adequately sort waste.

Potential difficulties of release prior reuse or recycling are usually associated with cost aspects, complexity of administrative clearance procedure and potential concern associated with the origin of cleared materials.

6.2.3 Lessons Learnt

Case studies illustrate various approaches (already existing experience and on-going R&D projects) considering Circular economy aspects and related to operation and decommissioning of nuclear facilities and management of radioactive materials and waste.

Those experiences highlighted that flexibility is required to move from linear to more circular approaches.

As decommissioning and radioactive waste and material management strategies are strongly influenced by national contexts and national regulations, change of the regulatory framework may be required or at least considered. This is outlined in the UK (investigating alternative end states) or the French (considering alternatives to storage approaches) case studies.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Alternatives options need to demonstrate an overall benefit with regards to the protection of human and the environment. Such benefit is related to a multiple range of criteria which are not related only to radiological risk management. This is outlined in most case studies and discussed in detail in WP4 Task 4.2c. The nuclear industry could probably benefit from conventional industry good practices, such as CLAIRE framework when it comes to site remediation for instance.

Dialog between stakeholders, including licensees, various regulatory bodies, waste management organizations, local stakeholders, etc. is needed to highlight advantages of novel approaches and demonstrating that more circular approaches are compatible with high nuclear safety and radiological protection standards.

Most stakeholders agree that additional regulation is not required, and harmonization is difficult as national contexts within Europe strongly differ (disposal capacities, waste inventory, nuclear industry, etc.). Nevertheless, European technical guidance (update of RP89 for instance) or software (see RESRAD in the US) which would be supported by national authorities and Technical Support Organisation could strongly contribute to improve current practices with regards to sustainability and circularity in the nuclear industry. It could also facilitate stakeholders' dialog and building confidence in new strategies.

Finally, circular approach should provide an overall economic benefit. Cost efficiency is a key aspect of any dismantling or radioactive waste management strategy and building bridge with conventional industry may be an opportunity to get benefit from other experiences and promoting the adoption of proven solutions for recycling.

6.2.4 References

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6.3 T4.2c: Sustainability Assessment – Summary Results

6.3.1 Introduction

Phase 1 of the project, covering technical work packages (WPs) 3–5, identified key topics for further exploration in Phase 2. Among these, Task 4.2c under WP4 focused on developing a decision-support framework to compare linear and Circular economy practices in the nuclear sector. This annex provides flexible guidelines for evaluating linear and Circular economy practices in radioactive waste management. It includes insights from a Delphi study applied to decommissioning and a case study showcasing the application of Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA) to waste management. These guidelines, tailored to specific conditions such as data availability, regulatory requirements, and strategic goals, focus on relevant criteria to streamline evaluations, enhance transparency, and align outcomes with environmental, economic, and societal objectives.

A review of sustainability assessment methodologies in the nuclear sector revealed diverse approaches. Participatory methods such as Social Network Analysis (SNA), the Delphi technique, and MCA incorporate stakeholder input, while quantitative tools like the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Analytic Network Process (ANP) prioritize sustainability indicators. These approaches highlight the need for dynamic, adaptable frameworks to ensure long-term relevance and advocate for multi-dimensional criteria to address the sector's complex sustainability challenges [6.3.1], [6.3.3], [6.3.4].

Various sustainability assessment methodologies were reviewed, including Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), Strategic Impact Assessment (SIA), cost-benefit analysis, carbon footprint, ecological footprint, and Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA). Among the methodologies reviewed, MCA emerged as the most suitable, as it integrates environmental, social, and economic factors and, combined with its participatory and adaptable nature, fosters transparency, stakeholder engagement, and effective navigation of sustainability complexities. MCA supports ranking, selecting, and comparing alternatives by explicitly considering multiple criteria [6.3.5], [6.3.6], [6.3.7], [6.3.8]. It promotes flexibility and dialogue, enabling traceable decision-making and fostering collaboration among stakeholders. Criteria in MCA are typically grouped into categories, with an initial proposal as shown in Figure 6-5.

The subsequent sections provide a detailed discussion of the category and criteria selection process.

Figure 6-5 - First proposal of categories for the MCA (own work).

6.3.2 Methodology

6.3.2.1 First draft of categories, criteria and indicators

The project team, with extensive experience in multi-criteria evaluation across the nuclear sector lifecycle, developed an initial set of categories and criteria. This was refined through internal filtering and a two-round Delphi methodology involving external expert reviews. Results were further assessed in expert discussions.

Figure 6-6 - Selected categories and criteria for the first round Delphi study.

presents the categories and criteria established in the first Delphi round, serving as the foundation for subsequent evaluations.

Figure 6-6 - Selected categories and criteria for the first round Delphi study.

6.3.3 Delphi study

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

To come to a broadly shared and validated range of dimensions, criteria, description and indicators that can be used for the assessment of Circular economy approaches for nuclear decommissioning projects, a Delphi study was conducted. A Delphi study is a method commonly used in social science and humanities research when researchers aim to gather expert opinions to facilitate interactions or even consensus on a specific topic or issue [6.3.1], [6.3.2], [6.3.10]. The method builds on a structured, iterative process, in which experts are asked for their input on a specific topic or question, after which the received feedback is incorporated, and an adapted list of topics or questions is sent out for novel feedback and/or validation.

The Task 4.2c partners established the categories and criteria presented in Figure 6-6 as the starting point for this exercise.

In light of HARPERS T4.2c, experts were asked to provide their input on:

- a. Defining Circular economy in the context of nuclear decommissioning (included in Section 1.2),
- b. Providing a range of dimensions, criteria, descriptions and indicators to assess Circular economy approaches in nuclear decommissioning projects.

Initially, the request to participate in a Delphi study was sent out to 30 members of the stakeholder group of HARPERS WP4. Due to limited initial feedback, an additional 17 experts were addressed, drawn from the network and contacts of the researchers at SCK CEN coordinating the Delphi study.

During the first round – which was organized between April 18th and May 9th 2024 – a total of five responses were received. After iterations to the definition and criteria/descriptions/indicators based on the feedback from round 1, a second round was organized between May 17th and May 31st 2024. In this second round, a total of 8 responses were received, bringing the total of individual experts reacting to the Delphi to 9. These experts were also invited to an online workshop organized in June 2024, to provide final inputs and validation (see next section). The dimensions, criteria, descriptions, and indicators developed based on input from the Delphi study and workshops (see next section) are detailed in Section 6.3.5.

6.3.4 Workshops

6.3.4.1 Workshop 1: Brasov (HARPERS Annual Meeting, June 19th 2024)

During the HARPERS annual meeting, which took place in Brasov (Romania) in June 2024, WP4.2 participants met in person to contribute to the final selection and validation of the categories and criteria for MCA. During this event, WP4.2c leaders made a presentation to summarise the work developed by the subtask partners, including the goal, methodology and results. Later on, the list of categories and criteria was presented to the participants, who were

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

asked to select the most relevant and the least relevant criteria for each category. The goal of the activity was to identify redundant criteria and to foster dialogue between participants.

Results were collected and included in the definition of the final list of categories and criteria discussed in the Results section.

Task 4.2.c: MultiCriteria Assessment

CATEGORIES

		SOCIAL	TECHNO-ECONOMIC	HEALTH AND SAFETY	LEGAL	ENVIRONMENT
CRITERIA		<div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #ADD8E6; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Shift in infrastructure</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #ADD8E6; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Impact on landscape</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #ADD8E6; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Increase in traffic</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #ADD8E6; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Impact on local values and cultural practices</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #ADD8E6; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Impact on local knowledge and skills</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #ADD8E6; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Restrictions on future land use</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #ADD8E6; padding: 5px;">Participation in decision making</div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #D3D3D3; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Investment and maintenance cost</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #D3D3D3; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Employment</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #D3D3D3; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Decommissioning deadline</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #D3D3D3; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Feasibility</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #D3D3D3; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Power consumption</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #D3D3D3; padding: 5px;">Overall economic cost and benefit</div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #FFD700; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Exposure to hazardous substances</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #FFD700; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Risk of accidents (public and workers)</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #FFD700; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Recovery time</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #FFD700; padding: 5px;">Risk of natural disaster</div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #FF8C00; padding: 5px; text-align: center;">Compliance with the expected future regulatory framework</div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #90EE90; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Emissions to air</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #90EE90; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Contribution to climatic change</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #90EE90; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Noise, dust and odour generation</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #90EE90; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Generation of waste</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #90EE90; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Generation of materials</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #90EE90; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Soil and water pollution</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #90EE90; padding: 5px; margin-bottom: 5px;">Impact on ecosystems</div> <div style="border: 1px solid black; background-color: #90EE90; padding: 5px;">Use of natural resources</div>
	Copy and paste (only 1) sticky note that includes the most relevant criteria for each category					
	Copy and paste (only 1) sticky note that includes the less relevant criteria for each category					

Figure 6-7 - Poster presented at the HARPERS Subtask 4.2c workshop 1 in Brasov, for the identification of most relevant and redundant criteria.

Table 6-5 - Results of the Brasov workshop 1, representing the most critical and less critical criteria. The numbers indicate the sum of times a criterion was selected by different participants.

Category	Most critical criteria				Less critical criteria	
Environmental	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Generation of waste x6 </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Noise, dust and odour generation x3 </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Use of natural resources x2 </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Soil and water pollution x2 </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #f4cccc;"> Contribution to climate change x3 </div>	
Social	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Restrictions on future land use x5 </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Increase in traffic x4 </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #f4cccc;"> Impact on local knowledge and skills x3 </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #f4cccc;"> Impact on local values and cultural practices x3 </div>
Economy	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Employment x4 </div>	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Overall economic cost and benefit x3 </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #f4cccc;"> Decommissioning deadline x3 </div>		
Legal	New proposed criteria <div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #fff2cc; margin: 0 auto; width: 50px;"> Reversibility and traceability </div>					
Health and safety	<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #d9ead3;"> Exposure to hazardous substances x10 </div>			<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #f4cccc;"> Risk of natural disasters x3 </div>		<div style="border: 1px solid black; padding: 5px; background-color: #f4cccc;"> Recovery time x3 </div>

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

6.3.4.2 Workshop 2: Delphi study (online, June 28th 2024)

The second online workshop was organized in early June 2024. During this event, the outcomes of the Delphi study were presented and validated by the stakeholders. The outcomes of this workshop are summarized in Table 6-6.

6.3.4.3 Workshop 3: MCA applied to waste management (online, October, 17th 2024)

During the third workshop, the partners involved in Subtask 4.2c reviewed the results of the Delphi study conducted for the decommissioning case. Additionally, the ANDRA team presented findings from a case study demonstrating the application of Multi-Criteria Assessment (MCA) to waste management.

6.3.5 Results of the Delphi study

The tables below include the criteria selected per each category, providing a description and a set of indicators.

Table 6-6 - Results of the Delphi study after two rounds of consultation with the stakeholders and final discussions during Workshop 2

Social dimension

Criterion		Description	Indicator
1.	Shifts in infrastructure	Impacts of the decommissioning process on community infrastructures (e.g. public transport, energy, schools, hospitals, environmental monitoring network) close to the project site.	Investments cost or economic loss (euros), presence and coverage of infrastructures (e.g. public transport capacities, number of hospitals, electricity grid coverage)
2.	Perceived impact on landscape 'nice to have'	Community perception of the impact on the territory (including natural and anthropic elements) of the decommissioning process (e.g. dismantlement of buildings, construction of recycling installations, avoidance of raw material industries).	Satisfaction of community with changes in landscape, notably in relation to the impact on natural (biodiversity net gain assessment) and anthropic (footprint of built environments) elements.
3.	Participation in decision-making 'key importance'	Extent to which communities can participate in decision-making during and regarding the various aspects of the decommissioning process. Key aspects: opportunities to express differences of opinion; diversity of organizations involved; involvement of youth; public participation/input; level of involvement; recognised importance of effective consultation and engagement with all workers.	1: inform (provide information); 2: consult (gathering opinions); 3: involve (2 way dialogue); 4: collaborate (multi-stakeholder interactions); 5: empower (partnership)
4.	Impact on local knowledge and skills	Extent to which the decommissioning process impacts on local access to education and knowledge development, training and skill building activities (e.g. regarding recycling of materials and reduction of waste) and efforts to build and expand local leadership, taking into account also the longevity of these opportunities.	Qualitative scale Scoring determined based on key aspects such as investments in creation of jobs; investments in development and retention of skills; use of local workers and skills; diversity and inclusion measures, taking into account whether these benefits are short or long-term impacts
5.	Impact on traffic 'nice to have'	Traffic of vehicles (cars, trucks, trains, boats, ...) during the decommissioning process.	Number of vehicles/day, Tonnes/km, Satisfaction of community with changes in traffic.
6.	Impact on local values and cultural practices	Extent to which the decommissioning process respects and builds on local values and traditions , and material goods with cultural or historical significance.	Qualitative scale Scoring may consider for instance how building on community values (e.g. by reusing the decommissioned facility) can be perceived as balancing the negative economic effects from stopping the operation of the NPP
7.	Restrictions on future land use	Restrictions to use of land (e.g., for agriculture, farming, residential and recreational activities, nature areas) during and after the decommissioning process Including international, European, national, regional and local legislation, guidelines, recommendations.	Restrictions per ha of land, community desires regarding future land use

Environmental dimension

Criterion		Description	Indicator
1.	Emissions to air	Extent to which decommissioning process limits/increases emissions to air of polluting substances (in comparison to baseline).	Indicators as by legislation ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, g/day, etc) (European/ national/ regional and local regulations)
2.	Carbon footprint	Overall carbon footprint of the decommissioning process. Including direct and indirect GHG emissions (e.g. also including emissions from transportation activities) and avoided emissions derived by the implementation of measures.	Teq (CO_2)/year
3.	Noise, dust and odour generation	Vibration and dust originated onsite during the decommissioning process. European/ national/ regional and local regulations.	Indicators as by legislation (dB, European odour units ouE/ m^3)

4.	Generation of waste 'key importance'	Generation of waste (hazardous and non-hazardous) during the decommissioning process. Short term/ long term impacts have to be distinguished, notably for radioactive wastes.	t/year, % of materials designated as waste
5.	Power consumption 'key importance'	Power consumption.	kWh/a
6.	Materials reintroduced in circulation 'key importance'	Volumes of secondary raw materials and other materials (e.g. concrete, plastics, ...) being retrieved, recycled and/or re-used.	t/year retrieved, t/year recycled, t/year re-used, % of materials re-usable (categorized based on conditionality of re-use)
7.	Soil and water pollution	Emissions to surface and groundwater and soil , including heavy metals, inorganic pollutants and organic matter. Short-term/ long term impacts have to be distinguished notably for radioactive impacts.	Indicators as by legislation: Concentration of contaminants (g/m ³ , mg/L), pH, dissolved oxygen etc. (European/ national/ regional and local regulations)
8.	Impact on ecosystems	Including biodiversity, vegetation coverage, restoration of natural habitats, etc.	PDF/year (PDF: Potentially disappeared fraction of species) or gain in biodiversity
9.	Use of natural resources	Consumption of resources (metals, inerts, etc.) during the decommissioning process.	Tonnes Tonnes /year?
10.	Asset re-use or retention	Whole assets (e.g. buildings) being retained and pollution/waste avoided through these processes.	
11.	Minimization of use of new raw materials	Volumes of new materials of which the use is avoided (e.g. through replacing them with secondary materials or adapting processes - e.g. when having to construct new buildings or infrastructure in light of decommissioning process).	
12.	Nature regeneration	Footprint of area released back to nature.	

Health and safety dimension

Criterium		Description	Indicator
1.	Risk of accidents (public and workers)	The likelihood of an accident to happen in the context of the decommissioning process (including e.g. recovery and re-use of materials) and the impact of the accident on the community and ecosystem.	Risk level (ISO-regulated?). Fatalities/ year Incidence rate
2.	Recovery time	Estimate of time it would take to restore to pre-incident conditions in case of an incident during the decommissioning process, taking into account the concentration/activity of radiological compounds and other contaminant substances.	Years
3.	Risk of natural disaster	Capability of the sites and facilities involved in the decommissioning process to resist to foreseeable natural disasters (including floodings, droughts, storms, heat waves).	Risk assessment conducted and measures implemented. Level of stress test. Site or facility being able to resist maximum credible hazard severity in various natural hazard scenarios

Legal dimension

Criterion	Description	Indicator
1. Compliance with the expected future regulatory framework	Considering prospective aspects on future legislation that might impact on de decommissioning process (speculative). Including international, European, national, regional and local legislation, guidelines, recommendations.	Qualitative: very unlikely to very likely

Techno-economic dimension

Criterion	Description	Indicator
1. Investment and maintenance costs and return on investment	Capital expenditures and operating expenses of decommissioning process, and the returns they bring (e.g. cost of disposal avoided, cost of new materials avoided).	€/year – ratios of investments/returns
2. Employment	Contribution to increase or decrease in local workforce in context of decommissioning process (including e.g. recycling and recovering). Number of jobs created directly or indirectly (also in sectors impacted by decommissioning process).	% variation from baseline of active population/number of employees, number of jobs directly or indirectly created/lost in the short and long term
3. Decommissioning duration	Length of decommissioning process (including legal authorization).	years
4. Feasibility	Technical difficulties and possibilities/Proof of concept/ Feasibility of various decommissioning activities (including e.g. options for recycling, re-use, recovery, disposal).	TRL scale
5. Overall economic cost and benefit	Including potential net benefits coming from re-use of the land and recycling or re-using materials obtained through the decommissioning process.	€ or €/year

6.3.6 Case study: VLLW Management situation in France

Very Low Level waste (VLLW) is defined in the law of 9 October 2008³; it is waste mainly from nuclear power plants, fuel cycle facilities and research centres, produced during operation (including maintenance) or during monitoring and decommissioning. VLLW can also come from conventional non-nuclear industries using materials containing one or more natural radionuclides that are not used for their radioactive properties⁴.

The activity level of VLLW is generally less than one hundred becquerels per gram. However, the management of this waste warrants a radiation protection inspection. In addition to the VLLW classification of radioactive waste, other characteristics need to be taken into account for its management: radiological (radionuclide typology), physical (in powder form, liquid form, mass, volume, etc.) or chemical (presence of hazardous waste, toxic substances, etc.).

According to the French National Inventory, this waste comes from more than 70 sites, two-thirds of which correspond to sites and facilities of the main generators (EDF, Orano, CEA).

In France, by the end of 2021, 633,000 m³ of VLLW had already been produced, including 430,00 m³ disposed of at the dedicated disposal (Cires) and 203,000 m³ stored at generators' sites, according to 2023 French National Inventory edition. Note that almost 80% of the waste disposed of at Cires facility consists of metal waste and waste such as soil and rubble.

6.3.6.1 Current management options: treatment, conditioning, and disposal solutions

The Cires disposal solution

The current options for managing VLLW waste are essentially based on direct disposal. In France, this is centralized at the Cires facility. Before disposal, the waste undergoes a series of processes, including characterisation, treatment, and conditioning, to ensure proper handling and compliance with regulatory standards.

- **Treatment and conditioning operations for the Cires disposal**

Various treatment and conditioning operations can be carried out prior to the disposal step, either to optimise waste volume or to comply with waste acceptance criteria.

Volume constraints, linked to the capacity of the Cires disposal and the related cost, represent a major challenge for producers. They are constantly working on the densification of waste packages. The aim of these optimisations is to increase the filling rate of the packages and consequently reduce the number of packages to be put together, as well as the volume of conditioned waste to be disposed of. This also makes it possible to reduce transport to the Cires, which reduces the resulting environmental impact.

³ <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000019668803>

⁴ <https://www.french-nuclear-safety.fr/information/news-archives/asn-issues-its-opinion-on-the-management-of-very-low-level-waste>

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

To achieve this, producers organise their waste management by implementing, wherever possible, waste pre-treatment stages such as sorting, cutting into pieces, compacting and stabilising hazardous waste.

6.3.6.2 The Cires disposal

In 2003, Andra commissioned a disposal centre dedicated to VLLW at Morvillier/La Chaise near the Centre de Stockage de l'Aube (CSA) (dedicated to low- and intermediate-level short-lived waste, LIL-SLW). In 2012 additional facilities for grouping, sorting, treatment and storing radioactive waste from non-nuclear power operations were put into operation. The disposal center is called "Cires" or Industrial Facility for Grouping, Storage and Disposal.

The Cires is a facility classified for environmental protection (ICPE), operated by Andra and with a total surface area of 46 hectares. This centre is licensed to dispose of 650,000 m³ of VLLW (cf. Figure 6-8).

Figure 6-8 - Aerial view of Cires.

In 2022, Cires received 21,991 packages of VLLW, representing a volume of 21,389 m³. They mainly came from EDF facilities (around 38% of the total volume delivered), Orano (around 32%) and the Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission (around 24%). The remaining 6% contained VLLW produced by the non-nuclear power industry.

Since 2003, 528,573 waste packages have been disposed of, *i.e.* 451,259 m³, representing 69.4% of the total authorised disposal capacity.

The Cires is equipped with two presses, which can be used to reduce the volume of compactable waste:

- A packing press: with a capacity of 300 tonnes, suitable for compacting metal waste such as light scrap. In 2022, 864 m³ of light scrap were compacted by the packing press. A reduction rate of 4.7 was achieved.

- A baling press: with a capacity of 120 tonnes, dedicated to low-density waste (plastics, thermal insulation, etc.). In 2022, 3,031 m³ of plastic waste were compacted by the baling press. The reduction rate was 3.2.

Radioactive waste collected from generators other than nuclear power plants (hospitals, pharmaceutical laboratories or other industrial sectors, etc.) are to be sent to the waste collection building of the Cires, from where it is routed to different premises according to its physico-chemical characteristics.

In 2022, a total of 1,994 packages of radioactive waste were accepted at the collection building, representing a volume of 163 m³. Between 2012 and 2022, 970 m³ of radioactive waste packages were stored at the Cires facility, utilizing 16.2% of the authorised storage capacity.

- **Treatment options**

Some VLLW's are not directly disposed of to the Cires facility. This generally involves specific types of waste, such as liquid waste, or to a lesser extent certain incinerable or metallic waste, when VLLW is associated with low- and intermediate-level short-lived waste.

- **Incineration of solid and liquid waste: the Centraco-Cyclife facility**

Centraco's incineration unit treats solid and liquid combustible VLLW and low- to intermediate-level short-lived waste (L-ILW-SLW) generated by nuclear facilities or collected by ANDRA (e.g. waste from non-electronuclear activities: laboratories, hospitals, etc.). Cyclife France is authorised to process 3,000 tonnes of solid waste and 3,000 tonnes of liquid waste per year.

The incineration unit reduces the volume of waste by a factor of 10 to 20 and enables precise physico-chemical and radiological characterisation of the resulting waste. Incineration residues, mainly ash and slag, are encapsulated in a cement using cooldown methods before being disposed of at the CSA (dedicated to LIL-SLW).

- **Treatment of organic and aqueous liquids**

It should be noted that liquid effluents are not considered to be radioactive waste as such. However, nuclear facilities are likely to produce liquid waste, which is not managed in effluent treatment facilities. Therefore, this aqueous or organic liquid waste cannot be stored directly and must be treated beforehand. There is generally no categorisation between very low and low-level liquids waste, which are treated in the same processes.

Liquids are preferably treated by co-incineration with solid waste at the Centraco facility, when acceptance criteria are met, with subsequent management of incineration residues (ash, slag, etc.).

- **The melting of some scrap metals: Centraco-Cyclife**

The VLL metal waste processed by the melting unit of Centraco-Cyclife facility is mixed with LL-IL metal waste. It should be noted that this process is technically possible for VLL metal waste, but in fact, it is little used because of its cost.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

The melting unit reduces the volume of waste by a factor of 6 and enables precise physico-chemical and radiological characterisation of the waste packages.

The final residues from the melting process, known as slag, dust and ingots, are conditioned in accordance with waste acceptance criteria associated with the Cires or CSA disposals.

Centraco's melting plant is licensed to melt 3,500 tonnes of metal waste per year. Since it was commissioned, the melting unit has melted more than 26,000 tonnes of metallic waste (value at the end of 2021).

6.3.6.3 Main management options currently used for VLLW

Figure 6-9 summarises the main management options currently used for VLLW. Note that a significant proportion of this waste was found to have low levels of radiological activity, sometimes below the detection thresholds of radioactivity measurement equipment.

Figure 6-9 - Summary diagram of current management options for VLLW

• **Challenges inducing evolutions for a better sustainable management of VLLW**
The need to better manage the volume of waste to be produced

The 2023 National Inventory edition, which includes forecasts based on data at the end of 2021, identified between 2,400,000 and 2,4300,000 m³ of VLLW to be produced at term, depending on the scenario. The prospects for the production of VLLW therefore exceed the current disposal capacity of the Cires, as by end 2021, this facility had reached approximately 66% of its licensed disposal capacity of 650,000 m³. Additional management solutions are therefore currently being studied (as presented in Section 6.3.6.5). The mid-term solution is to increase the licensed disposal capacity of Cires to 950,000 m³, without changing the current footprint of the disposal zone and keeping the same safety level (as further detailed in Section 6.3.6.4).

In view of the massive production of VLLW waste expected in the coming decades, the lines of thought that emerged around ten years ago on the management of VLLW waste involve re-

examining the current strategy of '*all disposed of in a centralised disposal facility*', without calling into question the associated general safety principles.

In addition, it has been noted that a significant proportion of the VLLW has a low level of radiological activity, sometimes below the detection thresholds.

- **General regulatory principles and sustainability issues**

The French regulations, and in particular article L. 541-1 of the French Environment Code⁵, define the general principles of waste management to promote a Circular economy, such as a hierarchy of waste management methods, giving priority to reducing the production and harmfulness of waste "at source", reusing waste, recycling it or exploiting it, particularly for energy recycling, before eliminating it, as well as limiting transport, etc. Other inherent technical objectives may be associated, such as the availability of the processing channels. The importance of preserving the limited disposal capacity for VLLW radioactive waste at Cires quickly became evident.

In this context, the French National Plan for the Management of Radioactive Waste and Materials (PNGMDR) has prescribed in 2016-2018 the carrying out of initial studies on additional management methods for VLLW waste, such as recycling, densification or the use of decentralised disposal facilities.

- **Regulatory changes in 2022**

The national doctrine for radioactive waste management initially defined a management method since waste produced in a nuclear facility is classified as radioactive according to where it is produced and not according to its radioactivity (waste zoning principle). So, whether it is radioactive or not, waste from a 'Zone of Possible Production of Nuclear Waste' had until recently to be managed exclusively in the nuclear sector and disposed of at Andra facilities.

In February 2022, following a wide-ranging public debate on the possibilities and procedures for recycling, the French government changed the regulatory framework applicable to the management of VLLW by allowing recycling operations to be carried out on a case-by-case basis for radioactive waste, which currently applies to metal waste.

As a result, recycling operations for certain types of metallic waste can be carried out in specific, duly authorised facilities. This decision represents a major shift in the available management options for VLL metallic waste.

In terms of waste zoning, it is important to note that its scope is reviewed at each life stage of the facility's lifecycle (construction, operation, decommissioning), to optimise the amount of waste classified as radioactive.

⁵ https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/codes/article_lc/LEGIARTI000043974936

- **Main challenges to be solved**

The main challenge for the future management of VLLW waste, as defined by the regulations, is to come up with an industrial management plan that '*preserves storage capacity by taking into account the possibilities for increasing the density of the waste stored and for recycling certain types of VLL radioactive waste from the environment*' (Article D.542-86 of the Environment Code).

The associated objective for the management of VLLW waste is to build diversified processes, proportionate to the technical and economic challenges, from the point of view of nuclear safety, the hazardous nature of the waste and its environmental impact. The future sizing of the disposal facilities will depend on the management options (treatment, recycling) envisaged and then implemented for the different types of VLLW waste.

The challenges for the management of VLLW waste can therefore be broken down as follows:

- Improve knowledge of this waste to refine management options,
 - Reduce the volume of waste to be produced at source and then disposed of,
 - Promote the Circular economy and sustainable development: open up technically and economically appropriate channels for certain types of waste, whether for treatment or recycling,
 - Size and anticipate the future capacity of the radioactive waste disposals.
- **Definition of the management options**

The recycling of certain VLL metallic waste is now feasible in specific, duly authorised facilities.

When the derogation is granted, products resulting from recycling operations that demonstrate radioactivity levels below the reference threshold are no longer classified as radioactive substances. This regulatory change aligns France with recovery facilities available in other European countries. Moreover, this recent regulatory change meets the challenges of the Circular economy by enabling the recycling of materials in France, including those with significant added value. In light of this, several recycling projects are currently being studied and are presented below.

- **Recycling projects of scrap metals**

EDF is planning to build an industrial facility known as the Technocentre to recycle VLL metal waste coming from the dismantling of nuclear facilities. The aim is to produce, after melting, metal ingots whose radiological characteristics, which are controlled by regulations, guarantee that they can be used without any impact on health or the environment. These ingots could then be used in conventional industry as well. The facility will be designed to receive 25,000 t of metal per year.

The waste produced by the facility will be sent to Andra to be disposed of, mainly to the Cires but also to a lesser extent to the CSA. The waste produced will represent between 10 and 15% of the mass entering the Technocentre facility.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

The investment decision should be made within 5 years, with commissioning of the plant scheduled for 2031. The plant is expected to operate for 40 years.

- **Project RPN2 - lead treatment and recycling**

A project led by a consortium of three companies (Fonderie Lemer, Orano and Curium) aims to develop an effective, reproducible, viable and safe solution for recycling low-level radioactive lead from the nuclear sector. The project is designed to process 400 tonnes of VLL lead waste per year.

- **Other recycling projects**

Other recycling projects are also under study for the preparation, pre-treatment or management of VLLW, and are presented in the following paragraphs. The current lines of thought are presented, but further precisions may emerge in the future.

- A project being carried out as part of the Plan d'Investissements d'Avenir is to develop a facility for separating the components of electrical cables: a radioactivity-free metal core and a peripheral polymer sheath with potential surface contamination. The metals (copper, and aluminium) could then be recycled.
- As part of the studies prescribed by the PNGMDR, various concrete fragmentation and crushing processes are being studied by Andra to assess the feasibility of replacing the backfill materials currently used at Cires with concrete rubble from the demolition of civil engineering structures at nuclear facilities or from the dismantling of nuclear installations. The needs associated with Cires are estimated at around 2,500 m³/year of backfill material.
- A project conducted by Orano is studying processes for extracting radionuclides (uranium which is a resource), making it possible to envisage the recycling of aqueous liquids. These solutions would have the dual advantage of being able to recycle liquids containing natural radionuclides and minimise the use of thermal processes. Currently, a few hundred cubic metres of these liquids are processed every day.

Note that a change in the regulations is needed before these projects can be implemented at an industrial scale: at present, recycling projects can only be envisaged for metal waste.

- **Envisaged disposal options**

Various projects, at different stages of development, are currently being studied with a view to broadening disposal management options.

6.3.6.4 Prospects for extending Cires disposal capacity (Acaci project)

As mentioned before, Cires facility currently has a maximum authorised disposal capacity of 650,000 m³, of which 66% had been used by the end of 2021. The license capacity of the Cires shall be reached by 2028/2029 based on current assumptions of deliveries from waste producers. Further to in-depth studies to extend the operational duration of the repository by increasing disposal capacity up to 950,000 m³ without changing the footprint of the current disposal, Andra prepared the regulatory file that was submitted in April 2023. Prior to this

submission, a preliminary consultation was organized from May 5 to June 9, 2021. The application is currently in appraisal by the State services. A public inquiry has just ended with a favourable opinion from the investigating commissioner. This project is named Acaci (See Figure 6-10).

Figure 6-10 - Acaci project to increase authorised disposal capacity at Cires.

The project will ensure continuity in the management of VLLW for an additional operating period of twelve to fifteen years. The works, estimated to cost €21 million, could start in 2024 or 2025.

- **VLLW2 - A second centralised disposal facility for VLLW**

The project to create a second centralised disposal facility for VLLW is necessary because the disposal capacities of the Cires, including those of the Acaci project, will not be sufficient to dispose of all the VLLW forecast in the prospective inventories, even considering the prospects for recycling.

In order to ensure the continuity of VLLW management, the future VLLW disposal facility would have to be operational before the Cires is saturated, *i.e.* around 2040 if the Acaci project is implemented, under current waste management conditions.

This project responds to the request for action 'VLLW.2' of the 5th edition of the PNGMDR (Article 15 of the order of 9 December 2022), which asks Andra to suggest a framework for the search for a siting area, as well as a schedule for feasibility and design studies.

- **Decentralised disposals**

To preserve part of the disposal capacity of the Cires and the future VLLW2 disposal facility, facilities adapted to certain types of VLLW could be envisaged on or near sites producing large

quantities of VLLW (in particular facilities currently being dismantled or to be dismantled). This would also make it possible to limit the transport of radioactive waste.

These repositories are known as ‘*decentralised repositories*’ (as opposed to the Cires, which is a repository that ‘centralises’ VLLW radioactive waste at national level). CEA, EDF, Framatome and Orano, in conjunction with Andra, are carrying out a feasibility study for this type of facility. This study will include a comparative analysis of the environmental impact of this type of management compared with the option of sending the waste to Cires.

- **Disposal in conventional hazardous waste disposal facilities**

As an extension of the thinking on decentralised disposals, consideration could be given to disposing of VLLW waste in conventional hazardous waste disposal facilities.

There are currently four conventional hazardous waste disposal facilities in France authorised to dispose of low-activity waste from radioactive substances of natural origin. This waste mainly contains uranium and thorium, and comes from the hydrocarbon, phosphate fertiliser, forestry products and thermal electricity industries.

6.3.6.5 VLLW waste management options under consideration

Figure 6-11 - VLLW waste management options under consideration.

summarises the main options under consideration for the future management of VLLW.

Figure 6-11 - VLLW waste management options under consideration.

- **Feedback experience from the multi-stakeholder, multi-criteria analysis**

The different management options detailed in 6.3.6.5.3.6.3 were presented and discussed during a multi-stakeholder, multi-criteria analysis (MS-MCA) in 2023, bringing together various stakeholders (industry, waste producers, civil society, authorities). Several management options were compared based on various social, economic, environmental and technical criteria. The major lessons learnt from this MS-MCA are detailed in the following paragraphs.

Figure 6-12 - Overall MS-MCA methodology developed in the PNGMDR 2022-2026 framework.

In the framework of the French National Plan for the Management of Radioactive Waste and Materials (PNGMDR), guidelines dedicated to the implementation of MS-MCA were developed (cf. Figure 6-12).

Precisely, these guidelines imply 5 main steps divided as follows:

- **Step 1 – Mandate of the working group** - composition of the working group, drafting the mission statement, preparing the meeting schedule, *etc.*
- **Step 2 – Context description and purpose of the decision** - presentation of the context and the decision options to be analysed, sharing of the main problematic and adaptation of the exercise’s objectives,
- **Step 3 – Multicriteria Analysis** – identification and definition of the assessment criteria, weighting of the criteria,
- **Step 4 – Aggregation** - 2 by 2 comparison exercise using dedicated mathematical tools.
- **Step 5 – Conclusion** – sharing the main conclusions of the exercise.

It should be noted that the added value of these guidelines lies in the fact that they suggest **practical sheets** that can be **easily adapted to specific cases**.

This is how this flexible and practical methodology have been implemented for assessing the various management options of VLLW. The main aim of this MS-MCA exercise was to obtain directions helping to build the future industrial VLLW management scheme. This is how 6 meetings have been organized according to the steps detailed above.

- **Meeting 1:** Presentation of the different management options for VLLW, structure of the MS-MCA work and identification of new members,
- **Meeting 2:** Integration of new members and definition of the first criteria,
- **Meeting 3:** Identification of criteria,

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

- **Meeting 4:** Finalisation of identification of criteria,
- **Meeting 5:** Discussion about (i) the data related to the criteria and (ii) the weighting of these criteria,
- **Meeting 6:** Discussion on the best management options to select.

The aggregation phase has not been implemented for this exercise and more details are provided in the following sections.

- **Composition of the working group**

Figure 6-13 details the main participants of the MS-MCA exercise.

Chair	Ministry of the Environment (DGEC)
Electricity producers and waste producers	CEA, EDF, Orano, Framatome, Solvay, Andra
Civil Society/NGOs	ANCCLI, France Nature Environnement, Global Chance, Sauvons le Climat
Administration and nuclear safety authorities	ASN, DGPR
Other experts	IRSN, CNE
Local actors	CLI de Fessenheim, CLI CSM, élus locaux
Project leaders of treatment/recycling options	Fonderie Lemer, Sécher Environnement, Arcelor Mittal

Figure 6-13 - Main composition of the stakeholders group: ANCCLI - National Association of the Local Committee of Information; ASN - French Nuclear Safety Authority; CEA - The French Alternative Energies and Atomic Commission; CNE - National Evaluation Commission; DGPR - Risk Prevention Department (Ministry of the Environment); IRSN - Institute for Radiation Protection and Nuclear Safety.

The composition of the stakeholder group initially aimed to bring together different groups of actors such as the authorities, radioactive waste producers, representatives of civil society and other experts in the management of radioactive and conventional waste. At the first meeting to introduce the exercise, it was decided that this working group should be extended to include other stakeholders of importance: local actors and industrial project leaders of the management options analysed in the exercise. This is how around 20 participants joined the MS-MCA exercise.

However, it should be noted that, in practice, there were real difficulties regarding the attendance of local actors and project leaders. Indeed, as the meetings progressed, they lost interest in the exercise and did not attend the last meeting. This argues for the need to insist on the attendance required for this kind of long-term work. Indeed, contributing to all stages of the methodology ensures that the conclusions are fully robust and shared by all the involved stakeholders.

- **Selection and definition of the criteria**

Three meetings were dedicated to the identification, definition and evaluation of the criteria. This phase was the heart of the exercise, insofar as all the participants were able to suggest their criteria and express their views on them. Afterwards, discussions were held to reach an agreement on harmonising these various criteria. This helped each participant to share their

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

positions and debate the criteria of importance for assessing the different management options.

A total of 16 criteria were selected, grouped into 5 main categories: Technical issues, Health-Environment issues, Economic issues, Regulatory aspects, Social impacts. Figure 6-14 provides a detailed overview of these 16 criteria.

Technical issues	Volume of treated waste
	Performance of the option
	Maturity & feasibility of the option
	Timeframe for implementing option
Health-Environment issues	Greenhouse gas emissions
	Water consumption
	Saving/consumption of raw materials
	Land artificialization
	Nuisances linked to the intensity of the activity
	Discharge and emissions (excluding greenhouse gases)
Economical issues	Cost of management option depending on waste volume implied
	Number of direct jobs generated by the implementation of the option
	Qualitative impact on the local territory
Regulatory aspects	Necessary regulatory adaptation
Social impacts	Social acceptability
	Recovery/circular economy

Figure 6-14 - List of criteria selected for the analysis of the management options of VLLW

While the phase of identifying and defining the criteria was very interesting and instructive, it should be noted that when it came to assessing the criteria themselves, several questions arose. Indeed, beyond the choice of criteria, there is a need to work on a clear definition of these criteria, particularly about their evaluation methods: rating variable, unit, input data, available database, etc. It is also important to put these criteria into perspective with the options being evaluated. For instance, for the exercise associated with the VLLW management options, some options were still in the project phase, involving information that was sometimes confidential, overestimated or not available at all. The case of societal and economic issues is also open to debate, since the associated criteria are often qualitative and difficult to assess for options that are still in the planning stage. Therefore, it is necessary to define the limits of the evaluation beforehand, to clearly display the uncertainties inherent in the exercise.

Finally, discussions among the stakeholders also highlight the need to consider all life stages of the analysed options (e.g., construction, operation, dismantling), so that the comparison of all the options is as robust as possible.

- **Weighting of the criteria – Comparing options**

On the basis of the list of criteria defined at the previous meetings, the participants were asked to weight each of them by assigning a weight between 0 and 100. This task gave rise to large

discussions, particularly about the impact of the individual weightings on the final result. Indeed, depending on the actors involved, the weighting sets could be very different. Integrating these different weighting sets to produce a single prioritised list of options would *de facto* have led to an artificial homogenisation of the results.

The participants did not wish to apply the aggregation phase, consisting of the use of a mathematical tool for comparing 2 to 2 the different options. They felt that the selection and definition of the criteria stage had enabled genuine in-depth work leading to a consensus on how to evaluate the different management options, taking into account the sensitivities of each individual. The AMC exercise was therefore concluded on this consensus.

- **Conclusions and lessons learned from the MS-MCA exercise**

This MS-MCA exercise brought together various stakeholders directly or indirectly involved in the management of VLLW. Although some participants were unable to attend all the meetings, and more particularly the final exchanges, the discussions throughout the exercise did enable sharing of different sensitivities and points of view. The most relevant management options were put forward, without the mathematical method of aggregation being deployed, quite simply because ample time for discussion was given during the criteria identification and evaluation phase. Therefore, this exercise fulfilled its initial objective, since it provided directions for the construction of the future industrial VLLW management scheme.

Currently, the future management of VLLW is a key issue in France, as it is becoming increasingly urgent to preserve the storage resource and thus promote more Circular economy alternatives. As part of the PNGMDR, Andra has been examining future VLLW management options, including new alternatives for the recovery and treatment of this waste. This led to suggest the management options plan presented in this case study, which was submitted to the French authorities in 2023. Subsequently, a multi-stakeholders, multi-criteria analysis exercise was carried out to discuss these management options, and thus gather everyone's sensitivities. Today, this exercise has been carried out by adapting a flexible methodology, which is guiding the reflections for the definition of the future VLLW industrial management scheme, to be published in the coming months.

- **Lessons learned**

In terms of lessons learned, the table below details the main elements that can be highlighted.

Methodology

All the MS-MCA exercises differ in their topics, objectives as well as regarding the participants involved. It is therefore important to rely on **flexible methodologies** that can be easily adapted, even if certain steps are not applied (e.g., in our case, non-application of aggregation).

Once the MS-MCA exercise has been launched, it is again important to **maintain flexibility**, whether in adapting the initial objective to the stakeholders' requests, choosing and defining the criteria, etc.

Stakeholder involvement

It is essential to present the general methodology (and the timetable for meetings) prior to any MS-MCA exercise, so that participants understand the importance of following the different stages. This helps to emphasise the need for **regular attendance** at the various meetings.

In the same spirit, defining clear objectives for each meeting can help ensure high attendance.

It may also be important to devote dedicated time presenting the technical issues at stake, so that each participant has the **same level of information** and shares the **same vocabulary**.

The presence of a **neutral steering** provides a link within the stakeholder group and ensures that every interest is taken into account.

Choice of criteria

It can be difficult for participants to choose and debate on a set of pre-defined criteria. It is necessary **to ensure flexibility** in the selection of criteria, leaving each participant to suggest his or her own ideas.

Efforts need to be made to define **how criteria can be assessed**: description of the criterion, unit, rating variable, input data, available databases, etc.

It is important to **collect input data as early as possible** during the implementation of the MS-MCA, as the projects to be assessed are not all at the same stage, and some players can be reluctant to share information.

Weighting phase – Comparing options

The weighting exercise is all the more difficult/relevant given the number of criteria involved.

There is a need to agree on how the criteria will be aggregated and how the final choices will be made.

Aggregation phase

The aggregation phase can involve various methodological approaches: mathematical 2-to-2 comparisons, weighted averages, qualitative comparisons, etc.

This phase is not necessary for the success of the exercise, especially if sufficient time has been given to discussions beforehand, enabling the identification of main orientations on the options to be chosen.

6.3.7 Conclusions and recommendations

The implementation of Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) and Delphi studies in the context of nuclear waste management and decommissioning provide a robust framework for comparing linear and Circular economy approaches. However, several challenges have emerged during their application. One major issue lies in the selection and weighting of criteria. Determining which criteria are most relevant and assigning appropriate weights is inherently subjective, as stakeholders often prioritize different aspects strictly related to their own expertise or interests. These differences are particularly pronounced when evaluating the trade-offs between the traditional linear model and the emerging Circular economy approach, complicating consensus-building.

Stakeholder engagement adds another layer of complexity. Nuclear waste management involves diverse stakeholders, including regulators, industry representatives, local communities, and environmental groups, each with distinct priorities. Reconciling these varied perspectives is essential but challenging, particularly when introducing Circular economy principles, which may demand significant changes to existing practices. This diversity of views and the economic implications can make it difficult to achieve broad acceptance of the evaluation outcomes.

Data availability and quality further complicate the process. Evaluating criteria for linear and Circular economy approaches requires reliable data, especially for complex areas like environmental impacts, health risks, and economic viability. Limited or inconsistent data introduces uncertainty and can undermine the transparency and credibility of the analyses.

The methodological complexity of MCA and Delphi studies also presents challenges. While these methods are well-suited to handling multi-dimensional evaluations, they can appear overly intricate or inaccessible to some stakeholders, leading to misunderstandings or mistrust in the process. This complexity is particularly evident in the comparison of linear and Circular economy models, where the range of criteria and the interplay between them can be daunting. Additionally, the reliance on expert judgment in Delphi studies may introduce bias, particularly if the group of experts lacks diversity or adequate representation of all relevant perspectives.

Balancing short-term and long-term objectives is another significant challenge. Linear approaches often focus on immediate cost efficiency, while Circular economy models emphasize long-term sustainability and resource optimization. Resolving these conflicting priorities requires careful consideration and a balanced evaluation framework. Furthermore, differences in national and regional regulatory frameworks and cultural attitudes toward nuclear waste management create additional hurdles. These differences can result in disagreements over best practices and complicate the adoption of Circular economy principles, which may not align seamlessly with existing regulatory structures.

WP4 Circular Economy Summary Position Paper

Despite these challenges, MCA and Delphi studies have proven effective in facilitating comprehensive and transparent evaluations. Their application enables stakeholders to systematically compare linear and Circular economy practices, fostering dialogue and consensus-building. Addressing these conflictive points requires clear communication, iterative stakeholder engagement, and flexibility in adapting methodologies to suit the specific context of nuclear waste management and decommissioning. By doing so, these tools can support informed decision-making and promote the transition toward more sustainable practices in the nuclear sector.

The two exercises detailed in this annex serve as a guideline for selecting criteria and indicators for implementing Multi-Criteria Analysis (MCA) in the context of decommissioning and nuclear waste management. However, it is essential to note that the application of these guidelines must be tailored to the specific case, taking into account the unique technical characteristics and the diverse stakeholders involved in the process.

6.3.8 References

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